

22RPT04 RFMicrowave2

D8: Best practice guide on how to build calibration capability for electric and magnetic fields in a full frequency range (i.e., 10 Hz to 40 GHz)

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1 of 55

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

22RPT04 RFMicrowave2	1
1 Introduction	4
2 Parallel plate capacitors	6
2.1 Basic method using voltage calibrator	6
2.2 Method based on high-voltage generator	11
2.3 General remarks	14
3 Helmholtz coil.....	15
3.1 Basic method using Helmholtz coil.....	15
3.2 Method based on single loop Helmholtz coil.....	21
3.3 Frequency extension of Helmholtz coil based on power sensor	21
3.4 Alternative coil designs (simulations).....	24
4 Rectangular waveguides	27
4.1 Introduction	27
4.2 Measurement setup	27
4.3 Corrections.....	28
4.4 Instrumentation	28
4.5 Measurement uncertainty.....	28
5 TEM cells, μ TEM cells.....	30
5.1 General principles	30
5.2 Realization of the μ TEM cell and small reference probe standards	31
6 Tapered cells	34
6.1 Introduction	34
6.2 Instrument and Measurement Setup	34
6.3 Uncertainty.....	36
7 Fully Anechoic Room FAR (Chamber)	37
7.1 Design of FAR.....	37
7.2 Validation of the FAR	37
7.3 Instrumentation	38
7.4 Basic settings for field probe calibrations in a FAR.....	39
7.5 Standard Field method.....	39
7.6 Transfer probe Method.....	41
8 Electromagnetic Pollution Measurement Practices.....	43
8.1 UMTS and LTE Base Stations.....	43
8.2 Measurement Methods of Base Station Signals	45
8.3 Measurement Studies	47
8.4 Measurement Results and Discussions.....	48
8.5 Conclusions	52
9 Conclusion	53
10 References	55

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For further details about the RFMicrowave 2 project see the project website <https://rfmwii.cmi.gov.cz/>

1 Introduction

The development of reliable and traceable calibration capability for electric and magnetic fields is an essential prerequisite for high-quality measurements in many areas of science, industry, regulation, and public safety. Electromagnetic field measurements support a wide range of applications, including electromagnetic compatibility testing, telecommunications, industrial process control, validation of field probes and sensors, and assessment of human exposure to electromagnetic fields. Because these applications span a very broad frequency range and involve both electric and magnetic quantities, national metrology institutes and designated laboratories require robust calibration infrastructures that can provide traceable reference fields under controlled and well-characterised conditions.

This best practice guide reports the progress made in building calibration capability for electric and magnetic fields in the frequency range from 10 Hz to 40 GHz. The work addresses both low-frequency and high-frequency regimes and therefore includes several complementary calibration methods and facilities. The report covers low-frequency electric-field generation using parallel plate capacitors, low-frequency magnetic-field generation using Helmholtz coils and related designs, and higher-frequency calibration approaches based on rectangular waveguides, TEM and μ TEM cells, pyramidal or tapered cells, and fully anechoic room facilities. Taken together, these methods form a coherent technical basis for extending calibration services across a wide spectral range that cannot be covered by any single setup.

A key objective of this work is to strengthen metrological infrastructure by establishing practical, traceable, and validated field-generation systems that can be used for calibration of probes and sensors with known uncertainty. In this context, the deliverable does not consider calibration capability as an isolated instrument function, but as a complete measurement system composed of reference standards, mechanical structures, instrumentation, positioning arrangements, environmental controls, calibration procedures, and uncertainty models. This system-level view is especially important for electromagnetic field calibration, where the generated field can be influenced not only by the primary source quantity, such as voltage, current, or power, but also by probe loading, field non-uniformity, holder effects, mismatch, parasitic coupling, and environmental reflections.

The best practice guide is therefore closely aligned with the broader objectives of European metrology projects under EURAMET and Horizon frameworks, namely the strengthening of traceability chains, the harmonisation of advanced measurement methods, and the transfer of knowledge into sustainable laboratory capability. By developing and documenting practical calibration procedures across multiple frequency ranges, the work supports improved comparability of measurements between laboratories and creates a stronger technical basis for future accredited calibration services. It also contributes to reducing measurement gaps in application areas where reliable field probe calibration is increasingly important due to the growing complexity of electromagnetic environments and the continued expansion of wireless and electronic technologies.

An important aspect of the reported work is the combination of established metrological principles with targeted technical development. For the low-frequency range, the deliverable describes methods in which electric and magnetic fields are generated from calibrated electrical quantities and accurately known geometries, thereby ensuring direct traceability to established standards. For higher frequencies, where field generation and characterization become more dependent on transmission structures, antennas, and chamber performance, the work focuses on validated setups and transfer methods that allow the realization of known fields with suitable uncertainty. In both cases, the report emphasizes the need to identify the dominant influence quantities and to quantify their contribution through structured uncertainty evaluation.

The document also reflects the practical reality that calibration capability must be tailored to the characteristics of the probe or sensor under test. Different devices require different calibration environments depending on their operating frequency range, dynamic range, physical dimensions, isotropy, and intended application. For this reason, the deliverable addresses both frequency response and linearity, as well as issues such as probe orientation, usable calibration volume, and the interaction between the field source and the device under test. This approach is important for ensuring that the developed capability is not only technically sound in principle, but also usable in routine laboratory practice.

In addition to documenting implemented methods, the best practice guide captures development activities aimed at improving or extending capability. These include refinement of coil-based methods, extension of frequency coverage, development of reference probes for use in cells, and validation of anechoic-room-based

approaches for probe calibration. Such activities are important for ensuring that the resulting capability is sustainable and adaptable to future needs. They also support the long-term objective of enabling European laboratories to respond to emerging calibration demands in a coordinated and technically consistent manner.

Overall, this best practice guide provides a consolidated account of the methods, facilities, and metrological considerations involved in building electric- and magnetic-field calibration capability over a very broad frequency range. Its purpose is both technical and strategic: technically, it documents the realization of traceable reference fields and the associated uncertainty framework; strategically, it supports the strengthening of European measurement capability in an area of growing relevance for industry, regulation, and research. In this way, the best practice guide contributes to the wider EURAMET/Horizon goals of advancing measurement science, supporting innovation, and improving confidence in electromagnetic field measurements across Europe.

2 Parallel plate capacitors

This chapter describes the calibration of low-frequency electric field probes using parallel plate capacitor. Subchapter 2.1 describes basic method using just parallel plate capacitor and calibrator while the Subchapter 2.2 describes the method using parallel plate capacitor and high-voltage generator. The calibration procedures are taken from the literature [2.1 – 2.3].

2.1 Basic method using voltage calibrator

Low-frequency electric field E is generated between two parallel metal electrodes (area: 1 m × 1 m, typical distance: $d = 0.5$ m) connected to calibrated accurate high voltage AC source V_s (e.g. calibrator Fluke 5520A, Fluke 5522A, Fluke 5720A, Fluke 5730A, etc.).

$$E = \frac{V_s}{d} \quad (2.1)$$

The E is calculated using Eq. 2.1 where V_s denotes voltage of a calibrated high voltage source and d the measured distance between the electrodes. This setup allows generation of E which can be used to calibrate electric E -field probes and sensors at field strengths up to $E = 2$ kV/m in frequency range from 10 Hz up to 400 kHz.

Typically, two parameters are calibrated for all E -field sensors and probes using the same procedure, *i.e.* a frequency response at the certain E -field and the linearity of E at the certain frequency:

- **Frequency response:** Frequency response is typically measured in 10 Hz to 400 kHz frequency range at $E = 100$ V/m or in 50 Hz to 10 kHz range at $E = 2$ kV/m. However, other f ranges and different E could be used if requested by costumers. Frequency grade F4 is usually used, *i.e.* 10 frequencies per decade are measured using logarithmic frequency spacing.
- **Linearity:** Linearity is usually measured at certain frequency (typically between 50 Hz and 1 kHz) in the E range between 10 V/m and 2 kV/m. Linearity is usually measured in this low frequency range, because in this range the calibrators usually provide the highest voltages. Otherwise, linearity can be also measured at other frequencies. Dynamic range grade A3 is usually used at this single frequency, which means that more than three levels are measured, including (at one range):
 - a level that is within 10% of the probe's specified sensitivity,
 - a level that is within the linear mean of the probe's dynamic range and
 - a level within 10% of the probe's specified maximum indication capability.

Calibration setup

The DUT probe or sensor is inserted into the centre of the parallel plate capacitor at orientation that needs to be calibrated and a few readings from the DUT probe indicator is noted, Fig. 2.1. Isotropic probes and sensors are calibrated using the same procedure, except that each DUT orientation is calibrated separately. The maximal E -field that could be generated at a certain frequency is mostly limited by the maximal output voltage of the calibrator at the certain frequency.

Additional verifications before calibration:

- Metallic object in the surroundings might alter the electric field within the capacitor therefore the measurement setup should be at least 1 m away from any other metallic object. Otherwise, a larger piece of metal should be used to assess the immunity of the field to the surrounding metal object, and any variation should be included as additional uncertainty contribution.
- Parallel plate capacitor with 1 m × 1 m plates that are separated by 0.5 m has capacitance of 17.7 pF which gives the impedance of roughly 9 MΩ and 9 kΩ which is significantly higher compared to the resistance of the cables, therefore the loading of the calibrator up-to 1 MHz could be neglected. Moreover, the AC currents at 1 MHz are still sufficiently low therefore the compliance current of the calibrator should not limit the calibration range.

- The E -field is generated with a parallel plate capacitor which has low impedance at higher frequencies. This low impedance might be problematic for the generation a high field strength at higher frequencies and consequently the E might be harmonically distorted. Therefore, harmonic distortion should be always verified at the highest field strength and highest frequency. The level of each harmonic component should be at least 20 dB below the fundamental signal otherwise additional uncertainty contribution should be introduced.

Figure 2.1: Calibration setup for generating electric field with parallel plate capacitor and calibrator

Equipment and traceability

The parallel plate capacitor (e.g., $A = 1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$, $d \approx 0.5 \text{ m}$) is the working standard for E -field generation. The strength of the field is calibrated traceably to international standards by using a known AC voltage reference and geometries of parallel plate capacitor which are both calibrated traceably to international standards at other laboratories. Calibrator (e.g., Fluke 5520A, Fluke 5522A, Fluke 5720A, Fluke 5730A or other) could be used to apply appropriate AC voltage and frequency to the electrodes and generate the E -field. Long cables in a large loop around the edges of the electrodes are used thus the field between the electrodes is minimally disturbed due to stray E -field generated by the cables.

Electric field uniformity

The plates of the capacitor have finite dimensions which causes two phenomena:

- The axial electric field (E_z) within the capacitor is not perfectly homogeny especially around plates' edges (Fig. 2.2a).
- A stray electric field ($E_{x,y}$) exist in the capacitor, and its strength increases with increasing distance from the centre (Fig. 2.2b).

Therefore, additional uncertainty contribution (due to inhomogeneity of E -field due to non-negligible size and/or misplacement of the reference probe/DUT) should be included in the calculation. The uncertainty depends on the size of the DUT probe and positioning accuracy and repeatability (Table 2.1), i.e., the magnitude of uncertainty roughly equal to 0.5% of the generated E -field should be included if measuring DUT smaller than 16 cm.

Figure 2.2: Normalized axial – z (a) and stray – x,y (b) E-field within parallel plate capacitor as a function of z and x,y. The fields are normalized with central axial – z field. The contours are separated by the 0.02 (i.e. 2%) with 1 (i.e. 100%) being at the centre of the capacitor.

Mathematic model and uncertainty contributions

Probe error ΔE is derived from the Eq. 2.2. The corresponding uncertainty contributions are listed below.

$$\Delta E_z = (E_{z,x} + k_{r,x}) - \frac{V_s + k_{V,spec}}{d + k_d} + k_{E,hom} + k_{E,hold} + k_{E,probe} \quad (2.2)$$

DUT probe reading of electric field ($E_{z,x}$)

This value is an average of usually five readings from the DUT probe indicator display. Uncertainty of this value can be estimated as a difference between the maximal and minimal reading since the reading are usually quite stable. This uncertainty is assumed to have rectangular distribution. Sensitivity coefficient $c_x = 1$.

Correction due to the DUT probe indicator resolution ($k_{r,x}$)

The quantity corresponds to the least significant digit if the DUT display equals the finite resolution of the display. The uncertainty is estimated as \pm half the resolution (half the magnitude of the least significant digit) with rectangular distribution. Sensitivity coefficient $c_x = 1$.

Voltage applied to the electrodes (V_s)

This is the voltage of the voltage source that is applied to the electrodes. The value is assumed exact. All uncertainties are included in $k_{V,spec}$ correction.

Correction of applied voltage due to specification of the voltage source ($k_{V,spec}$)

The uncertainty is associated with the specification of the voltage source (calibrator). If additional amplifier or voltage transformer is used, then all specifications are considered. This uncertainty is assumed to have rectangular distribution. Sensitivity coefficient c_V is defined by Eq. 2.3.

$$c_V = -\frac{1}{d} \quad (2.3)$$

Distance between the electrodes (d)

This value is a mean distance between the electrodes as measured with a calibrated ruler and Vernier caliper (see Appendix A). The value is assumed to be exact. All uncertainties are included in k_d correction.

Correction of the distance (k_d)

The uncertainty is associated with the uncertainty of the distance measurements. This uncertainty is assumed to have normal distribution. The sensitivity coefficient c_d is defined by Eq. 2.4.

$$c_d = \frac{V_s}{d^2} \tag{2.4}$$

Correction due to inhomogeneity of the generated field ($k_{E,hom}$)

This correction is associated with the homogeneity of the E -field that was calculated (Fig. 2.2) and experimentally verified. This uncertainty contribution strongly depends on the size of the DUT sensor or probe (Table 2.1). The uncertainty can be in a range of 0.5% of the generated E -field for most probes. This uncertainty contribution is assumed to have normal distribution ($k = 1$). Associated sensitivity coefficient c_E is 1.

Table 2.1: Maximal DUT dimensions a_{max} (and corresponding uncertainties) where a certain E -field uniformity is obtained

max. DUT dimensions	Uncertainty contribution (%)					
	0.5%	1%	2%	3%	4%	5%
a_{max} (cm)	16	21	26	29	31	37

Correction of the generated field due to the presence of holder ($k_{E,hold}$)

The Styrodur foam holder might slightly alter the value of the E -field since it has relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_r > 1$ and thickness of 4 cm therefore additional correction was included in the mathematical model. The uncertainty can be estimated 1% of generated E -field with normal distribution. Associated sensitivity coefficient c_E is 1.

Correction of generated field due to the presence of the DUT probe ($k_{E,probe}$)

The insertion of the DUT also alters the value of generated E which shall be considered as additional correction. This strongly overestimated uncertainty is around 0.5% of the generated E . This uncertainty is assumed to have normal probability distribution ($k=1$). Associated sensitivity coefficient c_E is 1.

Table 2.2: Uncertainty calculation example at 2133 V/m and 50 Hz using Method A. Calibrator Fluke 5520A was used as a voltage source. Five readings of DUT probe were measured and noted.

Mathematical model of measurement:								
Ex_min	2133,7 V/m	$\Delta E_z = (E_{z,x} + k_{r,x}) \cdot \frac{V_s + k_{U,spec}}{d + k_d} + k_{E,hom} + k_{E,hold} + k_{E,probe}$						
Ex_max	2133,8 V/m							
Quantity	Estimate	Standard uncertainty	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution	Effective degr. Of freedom	
X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$			c_i	$u_i(y)$	v_i	
Vs	1000 V	0,000 V	rectangular	1,73	-2,08 1/m	0 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{U,spec}$	0 V	0,179 V	rectangular	1,73	-2,08 1/m	-0,373 V/m	1E+99	
d	0,4801 m	0 m	normal	1	-4338 V/m ²	0 V/m	1E+99	
k_d	0 m	0,00027 m	normal	1	-4338 V/m ²	-1,2 V/m	10	
Ex	2133,75 V/m	0,03 V/m	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,03 V/m	4	
$k_{r,x}$	0 V/m	0,03 V/m	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,03 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{E,hom}$	0 V/m	10,41 V/m	normal	1	1 /	10,41 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{E,hold}$	0 V/m	20,8 V/m	normal	1	1 /	20,8 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{E,probe}$	0 V/m	10,4 V/m	normal	1	1 /	10,4 V/m	1E+99	
ΔE	51,0 V/m	Calculated uncertainty:					26 V/m	2,E+06
		Expanded uncertainty of measurement:					51 V/m	
		Expanded relative uncertainty of measurement:					2,45 %	

Three calculation examples are shown in Tables 2.2 – 2.4, for 50 Hz, 100 kHz and 400 kHz. The uncertainty is roughly 2.5% of the generated field. The uncertainty does not change significantly with the frequency since the uncertainty of the voltage source is generally negligibly small.

2.2 Method based on high-voltage generator

Low-frequency electric probes can usually measure very high electric fields which can exceed 100 kV/m. In this case a basic method with voltage calibrator is not sufficient a high voltage generator should be used instead. The calibration setup is shown in Fig. 2.3. High voltage generator is connected to the parallel plate capacitor and to the voltage divider. The output of the voltage divider is connected to digital multimeter which can be calibrated together with the voltage divider. The generated field is defined by Eq. 2.5, where E_z denoted the E -field in z direction, V_{DMM} is low-voltage measured with digital multimeter at the output port of the voltage divider, R is a voltage divider ratio and d distance between the electrodes of the parallel plate capacitor. The DUT probe or sensor is calibrated at the centre point of the parallel plate capacitor. The maximal E -field that could be generated by this method could exceed 100 kV/m at 50 Hz.

$$E_z = \frac{V_{DMM} \cdot R}{d} \quad (2.5)$$

Figure 2.3: Calibration setup for generating E -field with parallel plate capacitor and HV generator. The exact voltage of the HV generator is measured with HV divider and digital multimeter.

Equipment and traceability

The parallel plate capacitor (typically $A = 1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$, $d \approx 0.5 \text{ m}$) is the working standard for E -field generation. The distance between the electrodes is measured by a laser distance meter (e.g., Fluke 424D) which can be calibrated traceably at another accredited laboratory. The high-voltage generator is auxiliary equipment which is not calibrated. The voltage of the HV generator (i.e., voltage applied to the parallel plate capacitor) is measured with a high-voltage divider and digital multimeter which is connected to the output of the divider. They should be calibrated altogether to provide traceably to international standards.

Mathematic model and uncertainty contributions

The mathematical model of for the E -field probe calibration using parallel plate capacitor and HV source is defined by Eq. 2.6.

$$\Delta E_z = (E_{z,x} + k_{A,x} + k_{r,x}) - \frac{(V_{DMM} + k_{DMM,A} + k_{DMM,spec} + k_{DMM,res}) \cdot (R + k_R) + k_{V,its} + k_{V,sts} + k_{V,T} + k_{V,prox}}{(d + k_d)} + k_{E,hom} + k_{E,hold} + k_{E,probe} \quad (2.6)$$

DUT probe reading of E -field ($E_{z,x}$, $k_{A,x}$)

This value is an average of usually five readings from the DUT indicator display. Uncertainty of this value is estimated as a difference between the maximal and minimal reading, since the reading is usually quite stable. This uncertainty is assumed to have rectangular distribution. Sensitivity coefficient $c_x = 1$.

Correction due to DUT probe indicator resolution ($k_{r,x}$)

The quantity corresponds to the least significant digit if the DUT display and is related to finite resolution of the display. The uncertainty is \pm half the resolution (half the magnitude of the least significant digit) with rectangular distribution. Sensitivity coefficient $c_x = 1$.

Voltage measured by DMM at the output of the voltage divider and corresponding Type-A uncertainty contribution (V_{DMM} , $k_{DMM,A}$)

The V_{DMM} is an average of usually at least ten readings from voltmeter that is connected to the output port of the HV divider. The Type-A uncertainty $k_{DMM,A}$ is estimated to be a standard deviation of the mean of all readings. This uncertainty is assumed to have normal distribution. Sensitivity coefficient c_{DMM} is defined by Eq. 2.7.

$$c_{DMM} = -\frac{R}{d} \quad (2.7)$$

Correction of applied voltage due to specification of the voltage measurement ($k_{DMM,spec}$)

The uncertainty is associated with the specification of the digital multimeter. This uncertainty is typically around 0.06% of the measured value and 0.03% of the measurement range. Typically, 1 V and 10 V ranges are used. The $k_{DMM,spec}$ uncertainty is assumed to have rectangular distribution. Sensitivity coefficient c_{DMM} is defined by Eq. 2.7.

Correction of applied voltage due to resolution of the voltage measurement ($k_{DMM,spec}$)

The quantity corresponds to the least significant digit if the DMM display and is related to finite resolution of the display. The uncertainty is \pm half the resolution (half the magnitude of the least significant digit) with rectangular distribution. Sensitivity coefficient c_{DMM} is defined by Eq. 2.7.

Distance between the electrodes and corresponding uncertainty (d , k_d)

The d is a mean distance between the electrodes as measured using a calibrated laser meter (e.g., Fluke 424D). The uncertainty k_d related to d measurement should be also calculated and should include Type-A, specification and resolution of the distance measurements. This uncertainty is assumed to have normal probability distribution. The sensitivity coefficient c_d is defined by Eq. 2.8.

$$c_d = \frac{V_{DMM} \cdot R}{d^2} \quad (2.8)$$

Voltage division factor of the HV voltage divider and corresponding uncertainty (R , k_R)

The voltage division factor R for is usually 1000. The uncertainty contribution for AC voltage at 50 Hz is typically 0.2% of the voltage division ratio R (for exact values see calibration certificate). This uncertainty contribution has rectangular distribution. Sensitivity coefficient c_V is defined by Eq. 2.9.

$$c_R = -\frac{V_{DMM}}{d} \quad (2.9)$$

Uncertainty related to the long-time stability of reference high-voltage system ($k_{V,Its}$)

Uncertainty due to long-time stability (drift) of the reference high voltage system is normally determined from several calibration certificates (from the history). Typical value can be 0.2% of the high-voltage V_S that is applied to the input port of the voltage divider and thus to the parallel plate capacitor ($V_S = V_{DMM} \times R$). This uncertainty contribution has rectangular distribution. The sensitivity coefficient c_V is defined by Eq. 2.10.

$$c_V = -\frac{1}{d} \quad (2.10)$$

Uncertainty related to the short-term stability of reference high-voltage system ($k_{V,sts}$)

Uncertainty due to short-term stability of the reference high-voltage system is normally determined during the calibration of reference high-voltage system. The short-term stability of the reference high voltage system can

be also estimated to be 0.2% of the high-voltage V_S that is applied to the input port of the voltage divider and thus to the parallel plate capacitor ($V_S = V_{DMM} \times R$). This uncertainty contribution has rectangular distribution. The sensitivity coefficient c_V is defined by Eq. 2.10.

Uncertainty related to the effect of ambient temperature on high-voltage system ($k_{V,T}$)

The reference high voltage system is usually calibrated at 23 °C which is also used in laboratory environment only, where the temperature is typically stabilized to 23 °C \pm 2 °C. Since the temperature deviation from reference conditions is very small also the uncertainty due to the temperature effect is considered small. In uncertainty budget calculation $\frac{1}{4}$ of specification of high-voltage divider (*i.e.*, typically 0.05% of the high-voltage V_S that is applied to the input port of the voltage divider and thus to the parallel plate capacitor) can be used as uncertainty contribution due to the temperature effect. This uncertainty contribution has rectangular distribution. The sensitivity coefficient c_V is defined by Eq. 2.10.

Uncertainty related to the proximity effect ($k_{V,prox}$)

The proximity effect can be validated at voltage 1000 V / 52 Hz. The high-voltage divider shall be moved across the protective cage and the output voltage is measured at different distances from the grounded walls or other energized structures. Minimum distance can be 10 cm (this minimum distance shall be considered when performing calibrations). The overestimated proximity effect can be estimated to be roughly 250 ppm of the high-voltage V_S that is applied to the input port of the voltage divider and thus to the parallel plate capacitor. This uncertainty contribution has rectangular distribution. The sensitivity coefficient c_V is defined by Eq. 2.10.

Correction due to inhomogeneity of the generated field ($k_{E,hom}$)

This correction is associated with the homogeneity of the E -field that is calculated (Fig. 2.2) and experimentally verified. This uncertainty contribution is the same as described above. It strongly depends on the size of the DUT sensor or probe (Table 2.1). The uncertainty is typically 0.5% of the generated E -fields for most probes. This uncertainty contribution is assumed to have normal distribution ($k=1$). Sensitivity coefficient c_E is 1.

Correction of the generated field due to the presence of holder ($k_{E,hold}$)

The Styrodur holder might slightly alter the value of the E -field since it has relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_r > 1$ and thickness of 4 cm therefore additional correction shall be included in the mathematical model. The uncertainty can be estimated to be 1% of generated E -field with normal distribution. Sensitivity coefficient c_E is 1.

Correction of generated field due to the presence of the DUT probe ($k_{E,probe}$)

The insertion of the DUT also alters the value of generated E which is considered as additional uncertainty contribution. This overestimate uncertainty is assumed to be 0.5% of the generated E . This uncertainty is assumed to have normal distribution ($k=1$). Sensitivity coefficient c_E is 1.

Typical uncertainty calculation example for 100 kV/m at 50 Hz shown in Table 2.5. Typical overall uncertainty equals 2.5% of the generated electric field. The uncertainty is very similar as shown in Subchapter 2.1 since the contributions from the insertion of the probe, field homogeneity and due to the probe holder are the most dominant.

Table 2.5: Uncertainty calculation example for Narda EPH-50F isotropic *E&B* probe calibrated at 100 kV/m and 50 Hz using high-voltage generator. Eight readings of DUT probe were measured.

Mathematical model of measurement:								
$E_{x,min}$	100,00	kV/m						
$E_{x,max}$	99,99	kV/m						
V_{DMM}	48,0123	V						
$k_{DMM,A}$	0,00142	V						
Quantity	Estimate	Standard uncertainty	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution	Effective degr. of freedom	
X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$			c_i	$u_i(y)$	ν_i	
E_x	99995 V/m	2,89 V/m	rectangular	1,73	1 /	2,9 V/m	8	
$k_{R,x}$	0 V/m	2,887 V/m	rectangular	1,73	1 /	2,9 V/m	1E+99	
V_{DMM}	48,0123 V	0,00142 V	normal	1	-2083 1/m	3,0 V/m	8	
$k_{DMM,spec}$	0 V	0,034 V	rectangular	1,73	-2083 1/m	70,7 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{DMM,res}$	0 V	0,00003 V	rectangular	1,73	-2083 1/m	0,1 V/m	1E+99	
d	0,4801 m	0,00027 m	normal	1	208278 V/m ²	56 V/m	1E+99	
R	1000 /	1,2 /	rectangular	1,73	-100 V/m	115 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{V,Its}$	0 V	5,5 V	rectangular	1,73	-2 1/m	12 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{V,sts}$	0 V	5,5 V	rectangular	1,73	-2 1/m	12 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{V,T}$	0 V	13,9 V	rectangular	1,73	-2 1/m	29 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{V,prox}$	0 V	6,9 V	rectangular	1,73	-2 1/m	14 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{E,hom}$	0 V/m	500 V/m	normal	1	1 /	500 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{E,hold}$	0 V/m	1000 V/m	normal	1	1 /	1000 V/m	1E+99	
$k_{E,probe}$	0 V/m	500 V/m	normal	1	1 /	500 V/m	1E+99	
ΔE_z	-4,7 V/m	Calculated uncertainty:					1234 V/m	1,E+11
E_z	100000 V/m	Expanded uncertainty of measurement:					2468 V/m	
		Expanded relative uncertainty of measurement:					2,5 %	

2.3 General remarks

Low frequency *E*-field probes can be easily calibrated in parallel plate capacitor where the calibrator or high-voltage source is directly connected to the plates of the capacitor. The probes can be easily calibrated up-to 2 kV/m between 10 Hz and 400 kHz or even up-to 1 MHz using the calibrator. However, the LF *E*-field probes can usually measure very high fields even up-to 200 kV/m and in this case the high-voltage generator shall be used. Unfortunately, this method is readily limited only to line frequencies 50 Hz or 60 Hz.

The capacitance of the parallel plate capacitor is usually quite small and consequently the impedance is quite small. Therefore, the current is usually significantly below the compliance limit of the calibrator or high-voltage source. Additionally, the impedance of the capacitor is usually significantly higher than the impedances of the cables and other connections therefore there is no need to introduce another uncertainty related to the voltage drop on the cable. If voltage drop is still problematic a four-wire connection could be also used for basic setup with the calibrator.

While it is quite easy to find materials with relative permeability $\mu_0=1$ for magnetic application, this is not the case for materials' relative permittivity ϵ_0 . Only free space or air have relative permittivity equal or close to 1 while the values of other materials could easily reach 2 (e.g., Styrodur foam). Therefore, the most dominant uncertainty contribution is the effect of the probe holder. Additionally, the probe that is inserted into the capacitor has also a certain relative permittivity therefore it also changes the field in the capacitor. Additional important uncertainty contributions are related to the field homogeneity and the coupling between the calibrated probe and plates of the capacitor. Typical overall uncertainty (normal distribution, $k=2$) is 2.5%.

3 Helmholtz coil

3.1 Basic method using Helmholtz coil

Helmholtz coil consists of two circular coils of equal diameter and equal number of turns parallel to each other along the axis through the centre of the coils (Figs. 3.1 and 3.2). The coils are separated by a distance equal to the common radius of the coils. Two coils are connected in series aiding to produce a nearly uniform magnetic field in a region surrounding the centre point of the axis between the two coils (point c). Helmholtz coil should be supplied by a constant AC current. However, Helmholtz coil has usually a relatively high inductance and ohmic resistance therefore most calibrators could not be used due to voltage compliance and inductance limitations. Alternatively, an audio amplifier which is designed for the inductive loads and has high compliance voltage (≈ 40 V) can be used, Fig. 3.1. Another alternative is using a high-power AC source (e.g., ITECH IT806-350-90) to generate currents up-to 10 A in a frequency range up-to 2 kHz or above, Fig. 3.2. The exact value of the AC current is in both cases measured with amperemeter that is connected in series with the Helmholtz coil or alternatively by measuring the voltage drop on shunt resistor.

Figure 3.1: Calibration setup for generating B -field with Helmholtz coil using function generator and audio amplifier.

Figure 3.2: Calibration setup for generating B -field with Helmholtz coil using AC power generator.

The magnetic field strength is calculated from known geometries of the Helmholtz coils and measured current. The generated axial magnetic field H_z in A/m (*i.e.*, magnetic field strength along the z axis) in the central volume of the coil is defined by Eq. 3.1, where $N_{1,2}$ denotes number of turns in coil 1 and 2, respectively, and I a common AC current driving the coils.

$$H_z = \frac{N_1 \cdot I \cdot r_1^2}{2(r_1^2 + a_1^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{N_2 \cdot I \cdot r_2^2}{2(r_2^2 + a_2^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (3.1)$$

Parameters r_1 , r_2 , a_1 and a_2 are dimensional parameters of the Helmholtz coil as shown in Figs. 3.1 and 3.2. According to the definition of the Helmholtz coil the following simplification could be assumed:

- $r_1 = r_2 = r$,
- $N_1 = N_2 = N$ and
- $2 \times a_1 = 2 \times a_2 = r$.

The axial magnetic field H_z at the centre of the coil (point c in Figs. 3.1 and 3.2) is thus simplified, Eq. 3.2. Magnetic field density B_z is calculated from H_z using Eq. 3.3, where μ_0 denotes magnetic constant (*i.e.*, $\mu_0 = 4 \cdot \pi \cdot 10^{-7}$ Vs/Am). According to Eq. 3.2 the AC current needs to be measured, number of turns needs to be counted and the radius of the coil needs to be measured. Additionally, it needs to be confirmed that a real Helmholtz coil is used during the calibration (*i.e.*, verification of geometrical assumptions listed above).

$$H_z = \frac{N \cdot I}{r \cdot (1,25)^{3/2}} \quad (3.2)$$

$$B_z = \mu_0 \cdot H_z \quad (3.3)$$

There are some additional verifications that need to be done before the calibration:

- Any metallic object in the surroundings might disrupt the magnetic field within the coil therefore the measurement setup should be at least 2 m away from any other metallic object. Otherwise, a larger piece of metal should be used to assess the immunity of the magnetic field to the surrounding metal object. Any variation should be included as additional uncertainty contribution.
- The magnetic field is generated with a Helmholtz coil which has high impedance at higher frequencies. Therefore, at higher frequencies and higher currents higher voltages need to be applied to the coil to generate high magnetic field strengths. That might cause overheating of the coil therefore the current should be checked before and after calibration at higher B .
- Similarly, overdriving the current source at higher B and f might cause the harmonic distortion of the current source that is also transferred to the B . Therefore, harmonic distortion should be always verified when measuring at the highest B and highest f . The level of each harmonic component should be at least 20 dB below the fundamental signal otherwise additional uncertainty contribution should be introduced as well.
- When generating very weak magnetic fields ($B < 0.1 \mu\text{T}$), care should be taken to account for the background magnetic field, especially at 50 Hz.

The maximal magnetic field that could be generated is usually limited by the maximal current that could continuously flow through the wire (*i.e.*, cross-section of the wire) or with the maximal current that could be produced by the current source. At higher frequencies the impedance of the coil significantly increases therefore the voltage compliance of the current source or amplifier starts limiting the maximal B .

Traceability

The Helmholtz coil is the working standard for magnetic field generation. The strength of the field is calibrated traceably to international standards by using a known AC reference current and known geometry of the Helmholtz coil which should be both calibrated traceably to international standards.

Field uniformity

A magnetic field inside the Helmholtz coil is highly homogeneous only at the centre of the coil (point c, Figs. 3.1 and 3.2), otherwise two anomalies exist:

- The axial magnetic field (B_z) within the Helmholtz coil is not perfectly homogeneous away from the centre or outside of the coil (Fig. 3.3a). The field is especially non-homogeneous close to windings.
- A radial magnetic field (B_r) exists in the coil and its strength increases with increasing distance from the centre (Fig. 3.3b). This field component also increases near the windings.

Both anomalies related to the homogeneity should be included in the uncertainty calculation.

Figure 3.3: Normalized axial - z (a) and radial - r (b) magnetic field within Helmholtz coil as a function of z and x. The B -fields were normalized with axial - z field at the centre of the coil. The orange squares denote the coils' windings.

Calibrated parameters

Typically, two parameters are calibrated for all magnetic field sensors and probes using the same procedure, *i.e.*, a frequency response at the certain magnetic field density B and the linearity of B at the certain frequency:

- **Frequency response:** Frequency response is typically measured in the whole frequency range of the probe at relatively low magnetic fields. Frequency grade F4 shall be used, *i.e.*, 10 frequencies per decade are measured using logarithmic frequency spacing.
- **Linearity:** Since 50 Hz is the frequency most frequently measured, calibration of linearity is usually performed at this frequency. Additionally, at this frequency higher currents can be applied to the coils. Dynamic range grade A3 is used at this f , which means that more than three levels are measured:
 - a level that is within 10% of the probe's specified sensitivity,
 - a level that is within the linear mean of the probe's dynamic range and
 - a level within 10% of the probe's specified maximum indication capability.

Uncertainty

The mathematical error model of the magnetic field probe calibration is defined by Eq. 3.4. Each uncertainty contribution is discussed below.

$$\Delta B_z = (B_{z,x} + k_{r,x}) - \frac{\mu_0 \cdot (N + k_N) \cdot (I + k_{I,spec} + k_{I,res})}{(r + k_r) \cdot (1,25)^{3/2}} + k_{B,hom} + k_{B,hold} + k_{B,probe} + k_{B,bg} \quad (3.4)$$

DUT probe reading of magnetic field strength ($B_{z,x}$)

This value is an average of usually five readings from the calibrated probe. The reading is usually quite stable. Type-A uncertainty is estimated as half the difference between the maximal and minimal reading from the DUT with rectangular distribution. Sensitivity coefficient c_x is 1.

Correction due to the DUT probe indicator resolution ($k_{r,x}$)

The quantity corresponds to the least significant digit of the DUT display due to finite resolution of the display. The uncertainty is estimated as \pm half the resolution (half the magnitude of the least significant digit). This uncertainty contribution is assumed to have rectangular probability distribution. Sensitivity coefficient c_x is 1.

Vacuum permeability (μ_0)

This quantity is permeability of vacuum. The value equals $4 \cdot \pi \cdot 10^{-7}$ H/m. The uncertainty contribution related to this quantity can be neglected.

Number of turns for a coil and corresponding uncertainty (N , k_N)

Number of turns is counted prior the calibration. If only one layer of windings is used, the number of turns can be exactly counted, therefore this correction and corresponding uncertainty is assumed 0. Some field distortion may arise at the beginning and at the end of coil windings, but uncertainty due to this effect can be also neglected.

The current through the coils (I)

This value is an average of usually at least ten readings from the amperemeter. The type A uncertainty is estimated to be a standard deviation of the mean of all readings. This uncertainty is assumed to have normal distribution. Sensitivity coefficient c_I is defined by Eq. 3.5.

$$c_I = -\frac{\mu_0 \cdot N}{r \cdot (1.25)^{3/2}} \quad (3.5)$$

Correction of the current due to the specification of the amperemeter ($k_{I,spec}$)

The uncertainty contribution is taken from the amperemeter specifications (e.g., HP 34401, HP/Agilent/Keysight 3458, Fluke 8508A or 8588A). The uncertainty has rectangular distribution. The sensitivity coefficient is defined by Eq. 3.5. If the current is calculated by measuring the voltage drop on shunt resistor, both uncertainty contribution of the shunt as well as voltmeter should be considered.

Correction of the current due to the resolution of the amperemeter ($k_{I,res}$)

The correction is estimated to be 0 A with associated uncertainty \pm half the resolution of the amperemeter (half the magnitude of the least significant digit). The uncertainty has rectangular distribution. The sensitivity coefficient is defined by Eq. 3.5.

Helmholtz coil radius (r)

This parameter is mean radius of the Helmholtz coil that is measured with the calibrated ruler and Vernier calliper prior to DUT calibration.

Correction due to uncertainty of the Helmholtz coil radius (k_r)

The uncertainty contribution is related to uncertainty of the Helmholtz coil radius, and it should include Type-A of the measurement, specification and resolution of the ruler. The uncertainty has normal distribution. The sensitivity coefficient c_r is defined by Eq. 3.6.

$$c_r = \frac{\mu_0 \cdot N \cdot I}{r^2 \cdot (1.25)^{3/2}} \quad (3.6)$$

Correction due to inhomogeneity of the generated field ($k_{B,hom}$)

This correction is associated with the homogeneity of the magnetic field that needs to be calculated and experimentally verified. This uncertainty contribution strongly depends on the size of the DUT sensor or probe and is usually between 1-2%, depending on the probe size. This uncertainty contribution is assumed to have normal distribution ($k = 1$). Associated sensitivity coefficient c_B is 1.

Correction of the generated field due to presence of the holder ($k_{B,hol}$)

The holder might slightly influence B -field, therefore additional correction should be included in the mathematical model. However, typically a Styrodur material can be used as a holder which has a relative permeability $\mu_r \approx 1$ especially at lower frequencies ($f > 10$ kHz) therefore this uncertainty contribution can be neglected too.

Correction of the generated field due to presence of the probe ($k_{B,probe}$)

The insertion of the DUT also influences generated magnetic field which is considered as additional uncertainty contribution. This uncertainty contribution can be roughly estimated as 0.5% of the generated B -field. This uncertainty is assumed to have normal probability distribution ($k = 1$). Associated sensitivity coefficient c_B is 1.

Correction of the generated field due to presence of the background magnetic field ($k_{B,bg}$)

In addition to the generated magnetic field, a 50 Hz bias magnetic field is usually present due to electrical installation and various loads near Helmholtz coil. This background B -field is included as $k_{B,bg}$ uncertainty contribution. This uncertainty contribution shall be estimated by measuring the residual magnetic field that is present at the place of calibration when no current is flowing thru the Helmholtz coil. This uncertainty is assumed to have normal probability distribution ($k = 1$). Associated sensitivity coefficient c_B is 1. This correction is required only for calibration of magnetic fields sensors and probes in frequency around line frequencies (either 50 Hz or 60 Hz).

Three calculation examples are shown in Tables 3.1-3.3. Typical overall uncertainties are around 2.5% of the generated magnetic field.

Table 3.1: An example of magnetic field probe uncertainty calculation is given for calibration at nominal field strength $B_z = 195 \mu\text{T}$ at $f = 50 \text{ Hz}$. A Fluke 8508A multimeter was used to measure the current. Five readings of DUT probe were measured and noted.

Mathematical model of measurement:								
I_{s_mean}	3265,0 mA							
I_{s_div}	1,0 mA							
$B_{x,mean}$	195,35 μT							
$B_{x,max} - B_{x,mins}$	0,09 μT							
			$\Delta B_z = (B_{z,x} + k_{r,x}) - \frac{\mu_0 \cdot (N + k_N) \cdot (I + k_{I,spec} + k_{I,res})}{(r + k_r) \cdot (1,25)^{3/2}} + k_{B,hom} + k_{B,hold} + k_{B,probe} + k_{B,bias}$					
Quantity	Estimate	Standard uncertainty	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution	Effective degr. Of freedom	
X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$			c_i	$u_i(y)$	v_i	
B_x	195,35 μT	0,026 μT	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,026 μT	4	
$k_{r,x}$	0 μT	0,003 μT	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,0029 μT	1E+99	
I	3,265 A	0,00098 A	normal	1	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	-0,06 μT	4	
$k_{I,spec}$	0,0 A	0,00270 A	rectangular	1,73	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	-0,16 μT	1E+99	
$k_{I,res}$	0,0 A	0,000003 A	rectangular	1,73	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	-0,0002 μT	1E+99	
N	36 /	0 /	rectangular	1,73	-5,4 μT	0 μT	1E+99	
r	0,542 m	0,00029 m	normal	1	360 $\mu\text{T/m}$	0,10 μT	4	
k_{hom}	0 μT	1,9 μT	normal	1	1 /	1,9 μT	1E+99	
k_{hold}	0 μT	0 μT	normal	1	1 /	0 μT	1E+99	
k_{probe}	0 μT	0,97 μT	normal	1	1 /	1,0 μT	1E+99	
k_{bias}	0 μT	0,4 μT	normal	1	1 /	0,4 μT	1E+99	
ΔB_z	0,4 μT	Calculated uncertainty:					2,2 μT	751308
		Expanded uncertainty of measurement:					4,5 μT	
		Expanded relative uncertainty of measurement:					2,3 %	

Table 3.2: An example of magnetic field probe uncertainty calculation is given for calibration at nominal field strength $B_z = 30 \mu\text{T}$ at $f = 1 \text{ kHz}$. A Fluke 8508A multimeter was used to measure the current. Five readings of DUT probe were measured and noted.

Mathematical model of measurement:

Is_mean	503,4 mA						
Is_div	0,15 mA						
Bx_mean	30,00 μT						
Bx_max - Bx_mins	0,06 μT						

$$\Delta B_z = (B_{z,x} + k_{r,x}) - \frac{\mu_0 \cdot (N + k_N) \cdot (I + k_{l,spec} + k_{l,res})}{(r + k_r) \cdot (1,25)^{3/2}} + k_{B,hom} + k_{B,hold} + k_{B,probe} + k_{B,bias}$$

Quantity	Estimate	Standard uncertainty	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution	Effective degr. Of freedom	
X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$			c_i	$u_i(y)$	v_i	
Bx	30,00 μT	0,017 μT	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,017 μT	4	
$k_{r,x}$	0 μT	0,003 μT	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,0029 μT	1E+99	
I	0,503 A	0,00015 A	normal	1	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	-0,009 μT	4	
$k_{l,spec}$	0,0 A	0,00030 A	rectangular	1,73	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	-0,018 μT	1E+99	
$k_{l,res}$	0,0 A	0,000000 A	rectangular	1,73	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	0,0000 μT	1E+99	
N	36 /	0 /	rectangular	1,73	-0,8 μT	0 μT	1E+99	
r	0,542 m	0,00029 m	normal	1	55 $\mu\text{T/m}$	0,016 μT	4	
k_{hom}	0 μT	0,3 μT	normal	1	1 /	0,3 μT	1E+99	
k_{hold}	0 μT	0 μT	normal	1	1 /	0 μT	1E+99	
k_{probe}	0 μT	0,15 μT	normal	1	1 /	0,15 μT	1E+99	
k_{bias}	0 μT	0,0 μT	normal	1	1 /	0 μT	1E+99	
ΔB_z	-0,1 μT	Calculated uncertainty:					0,3 μT	316678
		Expanded uncertainty of measurement:					0,7 μT	
		Expanded relative uncertainty of measurement:					2,2 %	

Table 3.3: An example of magnetic field probe uncertainty calculation is given for calibration at nominal field strength $B_z = 3 \mu\text{T}$ at $f = 10 \text{ kHz}$. A Fluke 8508A multimeter was used to measure the current. Five readings of DUT probe were measured and noted.

Mathematical model of measurement:

Is_mean	50,1 mA						
Is_div	0,05 mA						
Bx_mean	3,00 μT						
Bx_max - Bx_mins	0,01 μT						

$$\Delta B_z = (B_{z,x} + k_{r,x}) - \frac{\mu_0 \cdot (N + k_N) \cdot (I + k_{l,spec} + k_{l,res})}{(r + k_r) \cdot (1,25)^{3/2}} + k_{B,hom} + k_{B,hold} + k_{B,probe} + k_{B,bias}$$

Quantity	Estimate	Standard uncertainty	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution	Effective degr. Of freedom	
X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$			c_i	$u_i(y)$	v_i	
Bx	3,00 μT	0,003 μT	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,0029 μT	4	
$k_{r,x}$	0 μT	0,003 μT	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,0029 μT	1E+99	
I	0,050 A	0,00005 A	normal	1	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	-0,003 μT	4	
$k_{l,spec}$	0,0 A	0,00003 A	rectangular	1,73	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	-0,0016 μT	1E+99	
$k_{l,res}$	0,0 A	0,000000 A	rectangular	1,73	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	0,0000 μT	1E+99	
N	36 /	0 /	rectangular	1,73	-0,1 μT	0 μT	1E+99	
r	0,542 m	0,00029 m	normal	1	6 $\mu\text{T/m}$	0,0016 μT	4	
k_{hom}	0 μT	0,0 μT	normal	1	1 /	0,03 μT	1E+99	
k_{hold}	0 μT	0 μT	normal	1	1 /	0 μT	1E+99	
k_{probe}	0 μT	0,01 μT	normal	1	1 /	0,015 μT	1E+99	
k_{bias}	0 μT	0,0 μT	normal	1	1 /	0 μT	1E+99	
ΔB_z	0,0 μT	Calculated uncertainty:					0,03 μT	33787
		Expanded uncertainty of measurement:					0,07 μT	
		Expanded relative uncertainty of measurement:					2,3 %	

3.2 Method based on a single loop Helmholtz coil

As discussed above, multiturn Helmholtz coil have two limitations:

- The Helmholtz coils have large ohmic resistance and quite large inductance therefore the impedance of the coil increases with increasing frequency. Therefore, a quite large compliance voltage is required at higher frequency to generate a sufficient current to generate required magnetic field. Large voltage compliance requirement and inductive properties of the coil make laboratory calibrators useless for the application and the only possible solution is using the audio amplifier. However, the maximal output voltage of audio amplifier is also always limited by the DC power supply voltage. Therefore, it is quite usual that the maximal field decreases with increasing frequency, when audio amplifiers are used.
- A mutual capacitive coupling between the coils exist which cause that the current is not flowing just through in the wire, but it flows also through capacitive coupling. This effect is increasingly pronounced at higher frequencies. This effect can thus significantly affect the accuracy since the amper meter measure the whole current while only the current that flows through the wire contributes to the magnetic field. Therefore, the impedance of the Helmholtz coil shall be also measured to verify where the resonance frequency is, and the Helmholtz coil should be always used up to the frequencies that are well below the resonance frequency.

To overcome both issues a single loop Helmholtz coil exists. This coil contains just one loop on each side; both loops have the same radius and the distance between the loops equal to the radius of the coils. The ohmic resistance and the inductance of the coil is much smaller in this case therefore even the AC current function of the calibrators might be used. In this case the current does not need to be measured by ampere meter that includes many uncertainty contributions (Type-A, specification, resolution) but only the specification of the calibrator can be used. Moreover, the current output of the calibrator is much more stable than the voltage output of the audio amplifier therefore also the Type-A uncertainty contribution related to the probe reading can be reduced. Another benefit of single loop Helmholtz coil is significant reduction of the capacitive coupling between the loops; therefore, this coil can be used at higher frequencies too. The major drawback of the coil is that it has just two loops therefore the maximal generated fields are generally smaller.

Nevertheless, the theory, descriptions and uncertainty contributions that were discussed above are also valid for single loop Helmholtz coil.

3.3 Frequency extension of Helmholtz coil based on power sensor

The upper frequency limit of the single loop Helmholtz coil can exceed 1 MHz and in this case the calibrator not the audio amplifiers can be used to generate the currents. Moreover, the frequencies are also too high to be measured directly with the ampere meter or indirectly by measuring a voltage drop on a shunt resistor. Therefore, another approach was developed that uses a signal generator and RF amplifier to generate the current which is measured by an oscilloscope or power sensor as a voltage drop on 50 Ω termination (attenuator). This concept is shown and discussed in this subsection.

Coil geometry is a critical factor in achieving magnetic field uniformity for the calibration of magnetic field probes. The number of turns directly affects the maximum amplitude of the field strength. Upper frequencies are limited by the cable length, wire diameter of the Helmholtz coil and by the material used in coil turns as this may create parasitic effects. Therefore, to degrade these effects, the proposed Helmholtz coil shall be designed with a single turn configuration with a diameter of around 30 cm and 5 mm wire diameter. At MHz frequencies, the cables used for the serial connection of coils begin to radiate and create a secondary magnetic field due to the electric field based on Maxwell's equations. These effects become more significant when the physical dimensions of the cables are no longer negligible compared to the operating wavelength. Consequently, careful cable shielding, signal feeding point and direction, grounding and physical separation are also required to suppress undesired radiation patterns. For its purposed design, the Helmholtz coil shall be characterized by a VNA.

Critical performance parameters of Helmholtz coil are:

- uniformity field area of the single loop Helmholtz Coil
- time stability
- current measurements

- validation of the Helmholtz coil

Figure 3.4: The manufactured single loop Helmholtz coil

Uniformity field area of the single loop Helmholtz coil

Uniform field measurements of the Helmholtz coil can be performed by using a 5 cm diameter small loop antenna developed for magnetic field measurements. A 5 cm diameter loop antenna is suitable to measure the uniformity of the Helmholtz coils. The reference magnetic field of the small loop antenna can be calculated based on its antenna factors. The orientation of the coils during the measurements and the setup are shown in Fig. 3.5.

Fig. 3.5. Uniformity measurement setup

Time Stability

Time stability measurements can be conducted at 10 MHz and at certain magnetic field strength (e.g., 0.47 A/m) using the uniformity measurement setup with small loop antenna for the 5 minutes. The current shall be measured across a 50 Ω load using an oscilloscope. The stability of the amplifier output shall be checked by calculating standard deviations from the saved voltage values on the oscilloscope.

Current Measurements

To generate the magnetic field, a signal from the signal generator is applied to an RF amplifier and the RF amplifier output shall be connected to the Helmholtz coil through a 6 dB, 250 W attenuator to protect the amplifier from back reflections. The magnetic field strength is calculated from the current, which is determined from the voltage drop over a 50 Ω load measured with an oscilloscope (alternatively an attenuator can be used). The sinusoidal signal can be verified by oscilloscope, and the current for each frequency can be

calculated using precise 50 Ω impedance values from the certificate. (i.) Verification of the generated magnetic field strength by Helmholtz coil at high frequencies, (ii.) the small loop antenna and (iii.) a commercial loop antenna can be used to obtaining traceable coil constants up to 10 MHz frequency range. The general measurement setup is shown in Fig. 3.6.

Figure 3.6: Current measurement for magnetic field probe calibrations in Helmholtz coil

Validation of the Helmholtz Coil

To validate the fabricated Helmholtz coil, a small loop antenna with known magnetic field factors can be used. First, the small loop antenna shall be positioned at the centre of the Helmholtz coils, with its sensing axis aligned with the direction of the applied magnetic field. The output voltage of the loop antenna shall be measured using EMI receiver (e.g., Rohde & Schwarz ESIB40), Fig. 3.7. Measurements can be performed at a certain magnetic field strength (e.g., 0.2 A/m) over entire frequency range. The EMI receiver must be configured with the peak-plus detector at input 2. The magnetic antenna factors can be obtained by dividing the applied magnetic field strength with the corresponding output voltage measured at the loop antenna using the EMI receiver. The measurement setup is shown in Fig. 3.7.

Consequently, this study proposes the use of magnetic antenna factors obtained from impedance measurements derived from the S_{11} parameters of small loop antennas. By applying frequency-dependent corrections based on these magnetic antenna factors to the Helmholtz coil correction factor or coil constant, magnetic field traceability can be established using a common reference.

Figure 3.7: The schematic diagram of the Helmholtz coil measurement setup validation.

Typical uncertainty contribution using this method are shown in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4: Uncertainty calculation example for measurement in single loop Helmholtz coil using RF amplifier and oscilloscope.

Source of Uncertainty	Type	Prob. dist.	u^2 (dB)
Cal. factor of the HC coil, $U_{HC,Const}$	B	2	
Reflections from HC windings, $\delta_{HC,Wind}$	B	1.732	
Cal. Factor of the oscilloscope, U_{Sep}	B	2	
Cal. factor 50 Ohm load, U_{load}	B	2	
Uniformity field error@x-axis, $U_{x,Uni}$	B	1.732	
Uniformity field error@y-axis, $U_{y,Uni}$	B	1.732	
Time stability, U_{TSta}	B	1	
Alignment, U_{Align}	B	1.732	
Repeatability, δ_{Rep}	A	1	
Combined standard uncertainty ($k=2$):			0.47

3.4 Alternative coil designs (simulations)

This subchapter outlines the optimization of uniform magnetic field generation using Helmholtz and Maxwell coil configurations. By applying exact analytical solutions to the Biot-Savart law for circular current loops, one can maximize the available homogeneous volume for magnetic field probe calibration. The geometric optimization of coil sizes and positions yielded at least a 20% increase in the uniform field area. Additional analysis confirms that multi-turn coils have a negligible effect on field topology, provided the cross-section remains small relative to the coil radius. Experimental validation supports the theoretical models.

Introduction and Objectives

Calibrating magnetic field probes requires highly uniform magnetic fields, typically generated by parallel circular coil structures such as Helmholtz (two-coil) or Maxwell (three-coil) configurations.

While classic configurations minimize non-uniformity at the absolute centre of the symmetry axis, they do not intrinsically maximize the surrounding homogeneous experimental area. This project establishes a direct computational approach to optimize loop dimensions and separations, aiming to maximize the usable calibration volume (flatness deviation bounds of 0.1%, 1%, and 3%) driven by a single current source.

Figure 3.8: Helmholtz and Maxwell coil designs, composed by parallel circular coils with given dimensional and current ratios. Coordinate (0,0,0) represents centre of each coil structure.

Methodology & Computational Model

The underlying magnetic field distributions are calculated strictly via the Biot-Savart law. Since wire wound windings can be approximated by unconnected circular current loops (where coil thickness \ll coil radius R), we utilize the exact analytical solutions for off-axis magnetic field components B_x and B_r (Eqs. 3.7 and 3.8). The α , Q , B_0 are defined by Eqs. 3.9 – 3.11, and $K(k)$ and $E(k)$ are the complete elliptic integrals of the first

and second kind. By mapping these solutions across the x (axial) and r (radial) planes, we extract the 3D field flatness topologies.

$$B_x = B_0 \frac{1}{\pi\sqrt{Q}} \left(E(k) \frac{1-\alpha^2-\beta^2}{Q-4\alpha} - K(k) \right) \quad (3.7)$$

$$B_r = B_0 \frac{\gamma}{\pi\sqrt{Q}} \left(E(k) \frac{1+\alpha^2+\beta^2}{Q-4\alpha} - K(k) \right) \quad (3.8)$$

$$\alpha = r/R, \beta = x/R, \gamma = x/r \quad (3.9)$$

$$Q = (1 + \alpha)^2 + \beta^2, k = \sqrt{4\alpha/Q} \quad (3.10)$$

$$B_0 = I\mu_0/2\alpha \quad (3.11)$$

Figure 3.9: 3D representation of magnetic field flatness within Maxwell coil. Circles represent 0.1% (red), 1% (green) and 3% (blue) deviations.

Geometric Optimization Results

The optimization criterion was to maximize the largest inner circular area constrained by specific field flatness bounds (0.1%, 1%, and 3%).

Helmholtz Coil Optimization

By linearly varying the coil distance from the symmetry centre, the optimal coil separation is shown to be larger than the classic R distance.

Results: Optimizing for a 1% flatness deviation requires a coil distance of $1.0236 \cdot R$ (versus $1.0 \cdot R$), yielding a uniform area increase of 24% (0.3826 m^2) over the standard design.

Maxwell Coil Optimization

The Maxwell configuration requires optimizing both the side coil radius ($R_{1,3}$) and the side coil distance ($x_{1,3}$) from the middle coil. For practical single-source driving, we constrained all three coils to carry equal current.

Results: The original Maxwell design produces a complex "dodecapus" deviation boundary.

By tuning parameters to $x_{1,3} = \pm 0.7013$ m and $R_{1,3} = \pm 0.8232$ m (assuming $R_2 = 1$ m), the 1% flatness area increases by 29% compared to the original Maxwell geometry, and by 145% compared to the original Helmholtz geometry.

Figure 3.10: Modified Maxwell coil design magnetic field flatness for 0.1%, 1% and 3%, with best fit red, green and blue circle, respectively.

Multi-Wire Deviation

Simulations modelling a thick conductor (9 loops in 3 layers) demonstrated that multiple turns only reduce the absolute centre field by 0.005% and shrink the 1% flatness area by a negligible 0.10%, validating the single-loop approximation.

Experimental Validation

Measurements were conducted using a non-optimized Helmholtz coil ($r = 30.75$ cm, $I = 5$ A) and a Bartington Mag B single-axis flux gate magnetometer. Results showed center field measured at 14.480 μ T, closely matching the theoretical calculation of 14.621 μ T.

Uniformity: Magnetic field strength measured across 54 points along the Z-axis matched calculations within the probe's 3.5% uncertainty envelope. Discrepancies at extreme positions were successfully attributed to probe alignment sensitivity to radial field components outside the homogeneous zone.

The computational approach utilizing elliptic integrals provides a robust framework for designing high-volume uniform magnetic fields. Key takeaways:

- Targeting a specific homogeneity bound (e.g., 1%) prior to construction allows for mechanical specifications that increase the usable experimental area by >20%.
- Wire thickness and multiple coils do not severely penalize field flatness.

Experimental edge-case deviations highlight the need for precise sensor alignment mapping in non-homogeneous zones.

4 Rectangular waveguides

4.1 Introduction

A rectangular waveguide assembly can be used to generate a known field. Due to its limited dimensions, which are closely linked to the frequency range, the assembly is primarily used for calibrating miniature probes serving as an E -field transfer standard. A waveguide calibration path is particularly suitable for frequency bands where it is not possible to use a μ TEM cell meaningfully. This typically refers to frequencies ranging from hundreds of MHz to units of GHz. Here, the use of waveguides is limited to the frequency band of the dominant TE₁₀ mode. Theoretically, this is only an octave band, but in practice, the area of application is usually even narrower. Due to the high frequencies, we only consider measurements of probes that respond to the electric component of the field.

4.2 Measurement setup

The measuring assembly consists of a coaxial-to-waveguide transition, a horizontal waveguide section where the reference field is generated, and finally a waveguide termination. The reference position is shown in cross-section A–A and is in the middle of the waveguide [$a/2$, $b/2$], Fig. 4.1. Access for the probe is provided by a small hole (considering surface currents, the smaller the hole, the better). For the reference position, the vector E is parallel to the shorter side b . It is important to note that the distribution of the E field in the cross-section is not uniform – the highest intensity is in the centre, *i.e.*, at the reference position, and gradually decreases to zero toward the side walls of the waveguide.

Figure 4.1: Diagram of the measuring setup

If we consider the horizontal waveguide line to be lossless and the termination to be ideal, and if we also consider $\mu_R=1$, $\epsilon_R=1$ (the dielectric is air), then Eq. 4.1 can be written, where P denotes power passing through a waveguide, Z is waveguide wave impedance (TE mode) and a and b waveguide dimensions. Z is defined by Eq. 4.2 where Z_0 denotes impedance of free space ($120 \cdot \pi \Omega$), f input signal frequency and f_c cut-off frequency for TE₁₀ mode, which is defined by Eq. 4.3 where c denotes speed of light in vacuum.

$$E = \sqrt{\frac{2ZP}{ab}} \quad (4.1)$$

$$Z = \frac{Z_0}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{f_c}{f}\right)^2}} \quad (4.2)$$

$$f_c = \frac{c}{2a} \quad (4.3)$$

4.3 Corrections

For accurate measurements, it is necessary to know the parameters of the coaxial-waveguide transition. This allows the power P passing through the waveguide to be calculated from the power of the travelling wave (PIN) present at the input coaxial connector. At least for the purposes of uncertainty evaluation, it is also necessary to know the attenuation of the horizontal waveguide section and the reflection coefficient of the waveguide termination. For the most accurate measurements, corrections are calculated from the measured complex S-parameters of individual elements. There is a certain disadvantage associated with this method – it is necessary to have a waveguide calibration kit available for the corresponding frequency band.

4.4 Instrumentation

The following equipment is required for measurements:

- RF generator
- RF amplifier (when higher field strength required)
- power sensors and power meters
- a three-port levelling device (either a directional coupler or a power splitter)
- coaxial cables and adapters.

The combination of a levelling three port and a power sensor can be replaced by using a directional power meter. The auxiliary measurements can be carried out using a vector network analyser and appropriate calibration kits.

Figure 4.2: Practical demonstration of measurement in R22 waveguide.

4.5 Measurement uncertainty

The most common uncertainty sources include are:

- **A-type uncertainty:** Measurement repeatability.
- **Power level measurement:** Uncertainty of measurement by power sensors, influence of power meter resolution.
- **Levelling three-port device:** Uncertainty due to power splitter asymmetry or uncertainty of directional coupler characterization.
- **Adapter insertion loss:** Uncertainty caused by coaxial-to-waveguide transition properties.
- **Mismatch error:** Uncertainty caused by an impedance mismatch between the components of the measurement path.
- **Probe position:** Uncertainty due to the probe deviation from its reference position (the probe's position along the longer side of the waveguide and its angular rotation have a significant influence.)

-
- **Effect of standing waves:** The effect of standing waves in the longitudinal direction caused primarily by imperfections of the waveguide termination.
 - **Effect of higher harmonics:** Probe sensitivity to higher harmonics.
 - **Distortion of the field by a probe:** Distortion of the reference field caused by the presence of the probe in the waveguide.
 - **Waveguide dimensions:** Uncertainty caused by waveguide dimensional tolerances

With a properly constructed measurement setup, the resulting measurement uncertainty in the waveguide's nominal frequency band can be expected to be better than 1 dB. When applying complex corrections based on S-parameters, a resulting uncertainty of better than 0.5 dB can be achieved; the advantage is that these corrections allow us to get closer to the theoretical frequency band of the waveguide.

5 TEM cells, μ TEM cells

Low frequency electric and magnetic field probes can be calibrated in parallel plate capacitor and Helmholtz coil, respectively (frequencies up-to 100 kHz). Higher frequency probes (above 500 MHz or 1 GHz) can be calibrated in fully anechoic room (see Chapter 7). The calibration in the frequency range between roughly 100 kHz and 500 MHz can be performed in tapered cell (pyramidal cell), Crawford cell (*i.e.*, TEM cell) or GTEM cell (*i.e.*, Giga Hertz TEM cell). The tapered cell is discussed in Chapter 6 while TEM cells and μ TEM cells are discussed in this chapter.

5.1 General principles

Electric and magnetic field probes can be calibrated in a TEM cell, Fig. 5.1. In this measuring setup, the signal generator is connected to the RF amplifier. The output of the amplifier is connected to the Port 1 of the TEM cell. Port 2 of the TEM cell is connected to the input of the attenuator while a RF power sensor (or oscilloscope with 50 Ω termination) is connected to the output of the attenuator. Alternatively (especially at higher frequencies), an RF coupler can be inserted between the RF amplifier and the input port of the TEM cell, while the output of the TEM cell is simply terminated by a high power 50 Ω termination.

The electric field strength E_s , magnetic field strength H_s in magnetic field density B_s in a TEM cell are calculated using Eqs. 5.1 – 5.3, where the P denotes the net power in a TEM cell (roughly the power measured by the power sensor multiplied by the attenuation of the RF attenuator or the difference between the forward and reverse power which is measured by power sensors connected to the RF coupler), d is the septum distance and Z_0 is impedance of free space (roughly 377 Ω), Eq. 5.4.

Figure 5.1: Calibration setup for generating magnetic field strength in TEM cell

$$E_s = \frac{\sqrt{P \cdot Z}}{d} \quad (5.1)$$

$$H_s = \frac{\sqrt{P \cdot Z}}{d \cdot Z_0} \quad (5.2)$$

$$B_s = \frac{\mu_0 \cdot \sqrt{P \cdot Z}}{d \cdot Z_0} \quad (5.3)$$

$$Z_0 = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0}{\epsilon_0}} \quad (5.4)$$

Uncertainty contributions

Typical uncertainty contributions related to probe calibration in TEM cells are:

- **Uncertainty contributions related to calibrated probe:** Type-A uncertainty, resolution
- **Uncertainty of net power measurements of the TEM cell:** type-A, resolution, specification, calibration factor of the power sensor and corresponding uncertainty, uncertainty of attenuator, mismatch between power sensor and attenuator with corresponding uncertainty, *etc.*)
- **Uncertainty associated to the septum distance**
- Uncertainty due to the **deviation of the field when the probe is inserted** in a TEM cell
- Uncertainty due to the deviation of the field when the **probe holder** is placed in a TEM cell
- Uncertainty due to **inhomogeneity** of the field

The TEM cell can be only used in a TEM mode where electric field E and magnetic field H are both perpendicular to the direction of propagation (*i.e.*, no field component in the direction of travel). At low frequencies, only the TEM mode exists, but at higher frequencies the cell dimensions become comparable to the wavelength and TE and TM modes (*i.e.*, non-TEM modes) can propagate and the field inside the TEM cell becomes non-uniform and unpredictable. The maximal frequency depends on the septum distance, and it can be by the rule of the thumb estimated as $f_{max}=c/(2 \cdot d)$, where c denoted the speed of light and d largest cross-sectional dimension of the cell. Typically, the upper frequency limits are 400 MHz and 900 MHz for TEM cells having 20 cm and 10 cm septum distances, respectively.

Moreover, the TEM should be neither used at very low frequencies although the free space impedance 377Ω constant is in principle valid. This relation between the E and H should be used only when both quantities are in the far-field (*i.e.*, plane wave conditions) while this is not the case when frequencies below 9 kHz are used (E and H fields are not tightly coupled fields become quasi-static, coupling becomes: mostly capacitive E -field or inductive H -field, the TEM cell no longer behaves like a uniform transmission line, field uniformity degrades and the calibration based on 377Ω assumption becomes less meaningful). Therefore, the probes can be calibrated in a TEM cell above 9 kHz due to low frequency constrains, while on contrary TEM cell dimension, especially the septum distance, defines the upper frequency limit to which the probes can be calibrated.

5.2 Realization of the μ TEM cell and small reference probe standards

In Subchapter 5.1 field calculation from geometry and power is defined. However, in principle it is also possible to define the field in the TEM cell using calibrated a micro probe, which cannot be only use in TEM cell but also in a tapered cell, fully anechoic room (FAR) or for the verification of the field. In this subchapter we show how to build and calibrate small reference probe standard.

Small reference probe design

The small reference probe consists of a $10 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$ rectangular capacitive antenna and a high-impedance resistive transmission line. RF signals are converted to DC signals on a standard FR4 board using a low-barrier Schottky diode with very low capacitance. The output voltage is measured via a fibre optic cable using a high-input impedance (over $1 \text{ G}\Omega$) voltage meter circuit or measuring devices like the Digital Multimeter 3458A. The footprint of the small reference probe standard is given in Fig. 5.2 and in the scope of the project the first manufactured version photo is given in Fig. 5.3.

Figure 5.2: Footprint of the small reference probe.

Figure 5.3: Small reference probe.

Instrument and Measurement Setup

The calibration of the small reference probe is performed inside the μ TEM cell. The electric field strength generated inside the μ TEM cell is obtained by sensing the net power with a power sensor and is calculated using the Eq. 5.5, where E denotes calculable the electric field strength (V/m), P_{net} is the net power (W) and d the septum distance (m). The schematic representation of calibration of the small reference probe is given in Fig. 5.4. In this case the characteristic impedance of 50Ω is considered.

Figure 5.4: Small reference probe and μ TEM calibration setup.

$$E (V/m) = \frac{\sqrt{P_{net} \cdot 50 \Omega}}{d} \tag{5.5}$$

The μ TEM cell that was used for calibration of the small reference probe has the dimensions $290 \text{ mm} \times 148 \text{ mm} \times 86 \text{ mm}$, and a septum distance d of 37 mm . Its frequency range is $10 \text{ MHz} - 1 \text{ GHz}$, Fig. 5.5. Critical features for μ TEM cells include good mechanical stabilization and very rigid connector pins that should not move during connection.

Figure 5.5: The manufactured μ TEM cell.

Measurement Uncertainty

The most common uncertainty contributions and their distributions are gathered in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: Uncertainty calculation example for measurement in μ TEM cell.

Source of Uncertainty	Type	Prob. dist.	u^2 (dB)
Cal. factor of the power sensor U_{PowCal}	B	2	
Insertion loss of the μ TEM cell U_{IL}	B	2	
TEM cell septum height measurement error U_{Sep}	B	1.732	
TEM cell uniform field area U_{Uni}	B	1.732	
Impedance at the midpoint of the μ TEM cell U_{Imp}	B	1.732	
Mismatch δ_{Mis}	B	1.414	
Repeatability δ_{Rep}	A	1	
Combined standard uncertainty ($k=2$):			0.47

6 Tapered cells

6.1 Introduction

In general, TEM cells and anechoic chambers are the most used measurement facilities for generating a standard electromagnetic field for calibration of electric and magnetic field probes and EMC testing. For frequencies lower than a few hundred MHz, TEM cells are preferred because they require less cost/space. However, when used to generate an EM field at higher frequencies, such as the gigahertz band, the size and homogeneous field of a TEM cell become considerably smaller. Small TEM cells are suitable for measurements of small instruments, such as probes with a size of about 1/3 of the septum height. In conical cells, TEM cells and chambers can be used to cover a portion of the frequency ranges they cover, including the passband. Advantages include lower construction costs, less space requirements, lower RF power requirements, practical frequency band coverage, and ease of use. Conversely, anechoic chambers with standard transmitting antennas can be used to generate a homogeneous field over a wider area for frequencies higher than a few hundred megahertz. However, anechoic chambers require more space and are more expensive to build and maintain. Typically, we need to use both facilities to complete a probe calibration covering a wide frequency range from megahertz to gigahertz.

Cone cells allow for electric field probe calibration covering a frequency range of approximately 200 MHz–2 GHz. These frequency regions can encompass very close frequency ranges and bands between chambers and cells. Therefore, in many cases, we can complete a probe calibration in the 200 MHz–2 GHz frequency range using only a cone cell. The advantages of cone cells include lower construction costs, smaller footprint, lower RF power requirements, practical frequency band coverage, and ease of use.

6.2 Instrument and Measurement Setup

The schematic representation of the measurement setup used in the calibration of the electric field probe inside a tapered cell is shown in Fig. 6.1.

Fig.6.1: Measurement setup used in calibrating electric field probes inside tapered cells

The traceable electric field strength inside the tapered cell can be obtained using a transfer standard or a computable standard. If a computable field standard is used, the net power at the tapered cell input is calculated using a directional coupler. If a computable field standard is not used, calibration of the tapered cell is performed using a small reference probe with calibration factors obtained within a μ TEM cell, which is used as a reference field standard. Then, the customer's probe is calibrated. The operating frequency range of the tapered cell is 200 MHz – 1 GHz. Dimensions and tapered cell impedance equation are given Fig. 6.2 and Fig. 6.3.

Figure 6.2: General dimensions of the manufactured tapered cell and appearance of the calibration point.

Figure 6.3: Tapered cell impedance formula

Figure 6.4: The photo of the manufactured tapered cell by Tubitak UME in scope of the project

The electric field value generated in the tapered cell using the transfer standard method is obtained by multiplying the net power at the input of the tapered cell by the calibration constant obtained using a μ TEM cell and a small reference probe. The k_f denotes the frequency-dependent tapered cell constant and P the net

power at tapered cell input. The tapered cell manufactured within the scope of the project at UME Tubitak is shown in Fig. 6.4.

$$E (V/m) = k_f \left(\frac{V}{m} / mW \right) \cdot P (mW) \quad (6.1)$$

6.3 Uncertainty

Calibration of the electric field probe within a tapered cell involves components such as the transfer standard uncertainties, reflections and standing wave errors in the tapered cell, Table 6.1.

Table 6.1: Uncertainty calculation example for measurement in tapered cell.

Source of Uncertainty	Type	Prob. dist.	u^2 (dB)
Cal. factor of the power sensor: U_{PowCal}	B	2	
Insertion loss of the tapered cell: U_{IL}	B	2	
Tapered cell septum height measurement error: U_{Sep}	B	1,732	
Tapered cell uniform field area: U_{Uni}	B	1,732	
Mismatch: δ_{Mis}	B	1,414	
Correction factor of the small reference probe: δ_{SRP}	B	2	
Tapered cell standing wave error: δ_{SWE}	B	2	
Repeatability: δ_{Rep}	A	1	
Combined standard uncertainty ($k=2$):			1.20

7 Fully Anechoic Room FAR (Chamber)

7.1 Design of FAR

A Fully Anechoic Room (FAR) is a basically a shielded room with absorbing materials covering the walls, floor and ceiling. The design and which absorbing material to use in the FAR will depend on its intended usable frequency range. Ferrite tiles will have a usable attenuation up to around 1 GHz. For frequencies from around 1 GHz and higher pyramidal absorbers are used. For broadband usage both ferrite tiles and pyramidal absorbers might be necessary.

Care should be taken for connections in and out of the FAR. If the equipment under test is connected using fiber, care should be taken for the entry point. One possible way is the use of “wave traps” as can be seen in Fig. 7.1

Figure 7.1: Connection into the FAR

Any equipment necessary inside the chamber, for instance video cameras used in reading older analogue instruments, should be covered in absorbing materials as far as possible without interfering with their use. If possible, the equipment should also be placed behind the antenna to have as small reflecting surface as possible, by keeping them out of the direct line of signal.

It can be important to be able to repeatably place a field probe under calibration in the same place. This place can be marked by having a small laser pointer in the roof of the FAR, thereby giving the same location. This is especially important for calibration using transfer standards. Any masts or supportive stands shall be made of low-reflecting materials, as for instance Teflon or Styrofoam, which also accounts for screws, nuts and so on.

7.2 Validation of the FAR

Several different ways to validate a FAR exist for the calibration of field measuring equipment. One of the most common is by measuring the Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR). In this method the field strength is measured for several positions which is shown in Figure 7.2. The distance L_0 is the normal calibration distance. If the distance L is too short, then the far-field conditions for the antenna will not be met, causing the antenna gain not to be (more or less) constant, but instead it will be a function of the distance. To minimize this uncertainty contribution, it is recommended to keep all the measurement distances so that the Eq. 7.1 is satisfied, where L is the measurement distance, D is the largest aperture dimension of the horn antenna and λ equals wavelength. A constant field is applied for each position (e.g., for example 20 V/m). The difference in the maximum and minimum read field strength should for each frequency less than a pre-determined value, (e.g., 0.5 dB).

$$L \geq \frac{2D^2}{\lambda} \quad (7.1)$$

Figure 7.2: VSWR setup

7.3 Instrumentation

Antennas

For calibration of field probes the antennas most commonly used are standard gain horn antennas. The advantage of standard horn antennas is that they have a predictable gain and an antenna diagram with maximum gain in the boresight for their frequency range. Dual Ridge Horn (DRH) antennas can be used as an alternative. They are not recommended though as the radiation pattern for these antennas is not that the maximum output signal is in its boresight for their entire frequency range, but also for that their far-field distance can be quite long.

Power Amplifiers

To be able to generate a sufficient field strength, a power amplifier is usually used. The most important features of this will be its gain, maximum output power and linearity. One important check for power amplifiers is the one for linearity. An amplifier working in compression will also have harmonics of the output signal. Any harmonics or other spurious signals need to be at least 20 dB lower than the main signal, preferably at least 25 dB lower. Many power amplifiers are multistage amplifiers, where the final stage sets the maximum output power. A degradation in any of the earlier stages might not show up on a maximum output power test, but a degradation in the earlier stages is still giving decreased overall linearity. It is therefore recommended for regular checks of the linearity to detect early signs of degradation.

Directional Couplers

A directional coupler is normally used to regulate and monitor the power into the antenna. The most important features of the directional coupler are frequency range, loss, mismatch and power handling capability. The coupling factor should be determined with the power sensor measurement range in mind. A power sensor can show larger uncertainties at the respective end of their useable range. If it has too high an input power, it might have started going into compression. For too low an input signal, noise contribution might cause lower accuracy and higher uncertainty.

Probe stand

Whether the method used is the standard field method or the transfer probe method, the probe stand can influence the result by causing unwanted reflections. The probe stand therefore is preferably made from materials with low reflectivity, such as polystyrene or Teflon. Also, if smaller objects like screws and nuts are used, they should be made from non-reflective materials such as plastic.

7.4 Basic settings for field probe calibrations in a FAR

There are several possible ways to calibrate a field probe in an FAR. The most common ones are the standard field method or the transfer probe method, which are described more in detail in a further chapter. Regardless of the calibration method, some properties are usually also to be considered as part of a calibration.

Orientation

The orientation of the field probe when calibrated is depending on its intended use. Many field probes require to be calibrated for each axis, calibrating an individual calibration factor for each axis. On some field measuring equipment it is sometimes very difficult to determine in which direction each individual axis is orientated. For these types of equipment, it is important to determine the most likely way they are used and to indicate in the certificate on how the test object was oriented during calibration. For instance, small radiation badges are usually worn close to the body, and for them only one side is fully exposed to an unperturbed incoming field.

Isotropy

Unless the test object is defined to be used in any specific direction only or its individual axis are calibrated separately, its isotropic properties (directional sensitivity) should be determined. The isotropic property is however difficult to measure and therefore the anisotropic property is determined instead. This is done by allowing the test object to indicate an appropriate field strength (or power density) S in V/m (or W/m²) and then rotate the probe axially (one lap), lying horizontally in a vertically polarized E field, see Fig. 7.3.

Figure 7.3: Anisotropic response

Max and Min values are recorded, and the anisotropic property can be determined using Eq. 7.2 where $C = 20$ is used for field strength and 10 for power density.

$$A = C \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{S_{\max}}{\sqrt{S_{\max} S_{\min}}} \right) [dB] \quad (7.2)$$

Linearity

In theory, for each calibrated frequency and probe setting, the calibration is made with several different field strengths. In practice this will become quite cumbersome, so this is done for one or a few preselected frequencies. If a field probe has more than one selectable sensitivity range, it is recommended to choose the different field strength levels in such a way that the cover more than one sensitivity range.

7.5 Standard Field method

This calibration method is based on the generation of a traceable electromagnetic field using standard gain horn antennas. The test object is measured while placed in the generated field. The electric field at the test object is defined by Eq. 7.3, where G denotes the gain of the reference antenna, P_{FWD} Forward power at directional coupler and L distance from antenna aperture to test object. The calibration factor is defined by Eq. 7.4 where E_{ref} is the (calculated) reference level of the electric field, and E_{DUT} is the test object readout of the same field.

$$E_{ref} = \frac{\sqrt{30G}}{L} \cdot \sqrt{P_{FWD}} \quad (7.3)$$

$$c = \frac{E_{ref}}{E_{DUT}} \quad (7.4)$$

From Eq. 7.3 it is to be seen that the traceability requires that the power, the reference antenna gain, and the test object's position (that is distance from the test antenna) can be determined in a traceable way.

A possible setup can be seen in Fig. 7.4. A signal generator is used to regulate the frequency and the field strength during calibration. It is connected to a wide band amplifier, which in turn is connected to a dual-directional coupler. The purpose of the directional coupler is to detect the forward and reverse power using a power meter. The value of the power meter is related to the generated reference electrical field strength at the test object. From the directional coupler a shielded cable is inserted into the FAR where the horn antenna is mounted. It is to be noted that it is fully possible to regulate the field strength by varying the gain of the power amplifier. This is not recommended as the linearity will also vary for each different gain setting.

Figure 7.4: Test setup.

Typical uncertainty contributions

Some of the most common sources for uncertainty are:

- **Power measurement:** To accurately determine the actual power being delivered into the antenna. Also, any losses in cables, directional couplers and mismatch needs to be adjusted for.
- **Antenna Gain:** The antenna gain usually comes from a calibration, although simulated results also can occur. The uncertainty from this calibration/simulation will impact the overall uncertainty of the field probe calibration.
- **Standing waves in the anechoic chamber:** Any reflective material inside the FAR can cause additional waves, which will cause local variations in the field uniformity. This is usually measured through the chamber validation.
- **Repeatability:** One uncertainty contribution comes from repeatability, for instance from connecting and reconnecting of the cables.
- **Positioning of the test object:** This uncertainty can be estimated to be the sum of several contributions. It is the uncertainty in distance between antenna and test object, in three dimensions (X, Y, Z). If there is an angular difference between the field generated and the test object this will also give a contribution needed to be accounted for. For some test devices it might also not be possible to determine exactly where the field sensors are located inside the test object.
- **Mismatch:** Any mismatch between different parts, for instance cables, directional coupler antennas, of the setup will result in a decrease in power delivered to the antenna.
- **Drift:** Various instruments, for instance power sensors, have a drift that come from time, but also from changes in temperature. Regular re-calibration of the instruments will decrease the contribution from this uncertainty.

7.6 Transfer probe Method

The transfer standard method uses a method where an already calibrated standard, the transfer standard, is used. The calibration of the test object is performed in an anechoic chamber in front of a transmitting antenna, where the readout from the test object is compared of the reference level indicated by the transfer field probe.

The transfer standard is usually traceably calibrated by other means, for instance it can in be calibrated using a μ TEM-cell or a GTEM-cell.

A signal generator is used to regulate the frequency and field strength during the calibration. It is connected to the amplifier which in turn is connected to a directional coupler. The directional coupler detects the forward power using a power meter. From the directional coupler a shielded cable is going into the anechoic chamber and to the transmitting antenna, Fig. 7.5.

Figure 7.5: Setting up the transmitting parts.

The transfer field probe and the test object are placed in the far-field region in front of the transmitting antenna. The same probe stand should be used for both the transfer standard as well as for the equipment under test. No scattering object (wood, steel, turntable etc.) may be present in the test object or transfer probe immediate vicinity. In the far-field region, the electric field in front of an antenna can be described by Eq. 7.5, where P denotes radiated power, G antenna gain and R the distance to the transfer probe / test object. The calibration factor of the test object is defined by Eq. 7.6.

$$E = \frac{\sqrt{30P \cdot G}}{R} \quad (7.5)$$

$$k = \frac{E_{ref,DUT}}{E_{DUT}} \quad (7.6)$$

In Eq. 7.6 $E_{ref,DUT}$ denotes the reference field in the chamber as estimated by this method when the test object is present in the chamber. Now, by combining Eqs. 7.5 with 7.6, the calibration factor of the test object can be expressed, Eq. 7.7, where index T marks the transfer probe measurement, index DUT marks test object measurement, k is test object calibration factor, c transfer probe calibration factor, E_T reading from transfer probe, P_{DUT} Directional coupler forward power, P_T Directional coupler forward power, G_T antenna gain during transfer probe measurement, G_{DUT} antenna gain during test object measurement, R_T distance antenna to transfer probe and R_{DUT} distance antenna to test object.

$$k = \frac{E_{ref,DUT}}{E_{DUT}} = \frac{c \cdot E_T \sqrt{\frac{P_{DUT} G_{DUT}}{P_T G_T} \frac{R_T}{R_{DUT}}}}{E_{DUT}} \quad (7.7)$$

The choice of transfer standard should be made with care. In theory the transfer standard should be of the same make and model as the test object. For instance, a transfer standard of a different size than the test object can measure a slightly different field strength, if there are (small) variations in the field uniformity. This is however impractical for a calibration lab to uphold.

Typical uncertainty contributions:

Some of the most common sources for uncertainty are:

- **Power measurement:** To accurately determine the actual power being delivered into the antenna. Also, any losses in cables, directional couplers and mismatch needs to be adjusted for.
- **Antenna Gain:** The antenna gain usually comes from a calibration, although simulated results also can occur. However, as the same antenna is used for both the transfer standard and the test object, this contribution is normally quite small.
- **Standing waves in the anechoic chamber:** Any reflective material inside the FAR can cause additional waves, which will cause local variations in the field uniformity. This is usually measured through the chamber validation.
- **Repeatability:** One uncertainty contribution comes from repeatability, for instance from connecting and reconnecting of the cables.
- **Positioning of the test object:** This uncertainty can be considered to be the sum of several contributions. The main contributor is the difference in placement of the transfer standard and the test object. If there is an angular difference between the transfer standard and the test object this will also give a contribution needed to be accounted for. For some test devices it might also not be possible to determine exactly where the field sensors are located inside the test object
- **Drift:** Various instruments, for instance power sensors, have a drift that come from time, but also from changes in temperature. Regular re-calibration of the instruments will decrease the contribution from this uncertainty.

8 Electromagnetic Pollution Measurement Practices

The broadband, frequency selective and code selective measurement methods used for EM pollution measurements of UMTS (3G) and LTE (4G) base stations are different measurement techniques and have their own advantages and disadvantages. In order to understand the relationship between them, the antenna and broadcast structure of the base stations should be examined. In today's mobile communication technologies, the base stations belonging to operators are separated from each other by different frequency bands, but the UMTS and LTE sector antennas of an operator in base stations can share the same frequency bands and broadcast at different power levels over the same band unlike Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM). UMTS and LTE base stations broadcast by using the same frequency band, that is, they are operated as a single frequency network. Each of these broadcasting sector antennas of the same operator is separated from each other by being coded with a different "Scrambling Code" for the UMTS and "Station Code" (Cell ID) for the LTE in the same frequency band.

Electromagnetic exposure measurements of these base stations are carried out by measuring the sum of the fields from all antennas and channels instantaneously with the frequency selective measurement method. However, with this measurement method, it is not possible to see the contribution of the electromagnetic field level from each sector antenna to the measurement result. In cases where one of these sector antennas is problematic or does not broadcast, it will not be possible to detect it with the frequency selective method. Especially in cases where the detection of the maximum radiation emanated from the base station is requested, the frequency selective measurement method will not provide precise and accurate measurement results. With the code selective measurement method, which is another measurement method, the limitations of the frequency selective method are remarkably eliminated. With the code selective measurement method, the station codes defined for each sector antenna can be determined separately and the cell-specific coded signals can be separated for each sector antenna and the maximum exposure level can be measured precisely by using extrapolation factors [8.1 – 8.2].

8.1 UMTS and LTE Base Stations

UMTS (3G)

UMTS (Universal Mobile Telecommunications System), the third generation (3G) mobile phone standard, is widely used in Europe. The main difference between GSM (2G) is that the data transmission rate is much higher. As it needs to be capable of high-speed transmission in a short frequency band, more transmission stations than GSM are required. UMTS and GSM systems share the same antenna in a base station. This is why frequency-selective measurements are required to find the total level of exposure resulting from UMTS signals. When we look at a UMTS spectrum, from the three broadcasting sectors each have at least one UMTS signal with a channel bandwidth of 5 MHz as shown in Fig. 8.1. The resolution bandwidth (RBW) must be 5 MHz, unlike the GSM signal. UMTS signals are WCDMA (Wideband Code Division Multiple Access) modulated signals.

Figure 8.1: Spectrum of sample UMTS (3G) signal.

UMTS signals have two different modes. These are the FDD mode in which a single common frequency channel is used for uplink and downlink, and the TDD mode in which separate channels are used. TDD is rarely used, usually FDD mode is used. Although the UMTS spectrum in Fig. 8.1 does not seem to be separated in the spectral measurement, determining and measuring the centre frequency will give the correct result in the instantaneous measurement. If the extrapolation factor (K) is known on the operator side and the measured signal is assumed to be P_{min} if the traffic load is assumed to be absent, then the maximum power P_{max} of the spectrum is found as in Eq. 8.1. RMS detector should be used in measurements [8.3 – 8.4].

$$P_{max} = K \cdot P_{min} \quad (1)$$

If there are adjacent channels in the frequency band, it becomes impossible to distinguish them by spectral method. Another method which is more preferred than spectral measurement in frequency selective measurement method is "channel power measurement". With this method, centre frequencies are used for each channel and only the measured signal is displayed on the spectrum display. Resolution bandwidth (RBW), video bandwidth (VBW), sweep time, number of points, span and detector type are set. Integration time is a very important parameter that needs to be set. However, if there are channels in the measurement that will cause traffic such as speech channels, P_{max} will be significantly more than expected. Another method used to avoid these disadvantages of spectral measurement is "code decoding" measurements. The code decoding measures the field strength generated by the CPICH (Primary Common Pilot Channel) signal of each antenna. The power of this signal is distributed over the full signal bandwidth of 5 MHz and is encoded by the encryption codes. If a base station is considered, the electric field for each of the 3 sector antennas belonging to this station is determined as in Eq. 8.2. The total level, as in Eq. 8.3, is obtained by the collection of the electric field levels of these sector antennas [8.5 – 8.6].

$$E_{sectorN} = CPICH_{powerN} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{P_{max N}}{P_{CPICH(N)}}} \quad (8.2)$$

$$E_{sum} = \sqrt{E_{sector1}^2 + E_{sector2}^2 + E_{sector3}^2} \quad (8.3)$$

LTE (4G)

LTE (4G) is a mobile communications standard for high-speed data transmission. Many different frequency bands have been allocated worldwide for LTE mobile communication in the frequency range of 400 MHz to 3600 MHz. Flexible channel bandwidths (1.4 / 3 / 5 / 10 / 15 / 20 MHz) and signal bandwidths (1.08 / 2.7 / 4.5 / 9 / 13.5 / 18 MHz) are used for LTE base stations as given in Table 8.1 instead of fixed channel spacing (200 kHz for GSM and 5 MHz for UMTS). LTE networks operate as Single Frequency Networks (SFN), and each antenna operated by a particular operator radiates its signals on the same frequency channel. As the transmission method for these signals (downlink), the Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) modulation is used, which divides the entire signal bandwidth into many subcarriers with carrier spacing of 15 kHz [8.7]. The Multiple Input – Multiple Output (MIMO) antenna technology is used in LTE base stations to provide data rate and spectrum efficiency. A MIMO system comprising two transmitting or receiving antennas is usually utilized for the downlink in LTE (2 antenna MIMO) and uses multipath signal propagation between the transmitter and the receiver. Two separate physical signals (downlink) are radiated or received simultaneously over conventional cross-polarized sector antennas with two dipole groups rotated by 90° ($\pm 45^\circ$) [8.8].

When we study the structure of an LTE signal in detail, the smallest time unit is the "symbol" and it is 70 μ s. 7 symbols that come together consecutively form 1 "slot" and cover a time frame of 0.5 ms. 20 slots that come together consecutively create a "frame" and its duration is 10 ms. In the frequency domain, the modulation method used (OFDMA) for the LTE signal includes many subcarriers, each separated by 15 kHz. The smallest unit of the time & frequency for the LTE signal, which is a subcarrier in a symbol (15 kHz x 70 μ s), is called a Resource Element (RE). 12 consecutive subcarriers and 7 symbols form a Resource Block (RB) [8.8 – 8.9].

Table 8.1: LTE typical channel and signal bandwidths

Channel Bandwidth (CBW)	Signal Bandwidth (SBW)	Number of Resource Blocks	Number of Subcarriers
1.4 MHz	1.08 MHz	6	72
3 MHz	2.7 MHz	15	180
5 MHz	4.5 MHz	25	300
10 MHz	9 MHz	50	600
15 MHz	13.5 MHz	75	900
20 MHz	18 MHz	100	1200

In LTE base stations, there are some signals that are cell-specifically coded for each MIMO antenna. These signals are Primary Synchronization Signal (P-SS), Secondary Synchronization Signal (S-SS) and Reference Signal (RS). The most important one among these signals is the RS signal in terms of exposure measurements because RS signals are the most stable signals that can be separated according to MIMO antenna channels. The RS signal is considered to be the most suitable signal to be measured and to calculate the maximum exposure for each LTE base station with the best accuracy. LTE signals can be transmitted in two different modes over antennas. These are the Frequency Division Duplex (FDD) mode, where separate channels are used for the uplink and downlink, and the Time Division Duplex (TDD) mode, where a common single frequency channel is used for both. Nowadays, the FDD mode is widely used whereas the TDD is rare [8.10].

8.2 Measurement Methods of Base Station Signals

Within the scope of the project, LTE signals were dominantly observed in the measurements we made around the base station. Therefore, discussions and comparisons of measurement methods were made for LTE signals.

Today, the measurements to determine the electromagnetic exposure caused by the signals emitted from LTE base stations are performed by frequency selective and code selective measurement methods using compact electromagnetic field measurement devices.

The SRM 3006 device that we own offers "Spectrum Analysis Mode", "Safety Evaluation Mode" and "Level Recorder" modes which can be used for frequency selective LTE base station measurements. On the other hand, frequency selective measurements using the spectrum analysis mode or the safety evaluation mode are not recommended because the signals to be captured with the frequency selective method are only very briefly present during a radio frame and the signal to be measured must be captured without any gaps if possible. This is ensured if the level recorder mode of the measurement device is used. Therefore, the most suitable mode for LTE measurements is deemed to be the level recorder mode whereas the spectrum analysis and safety evaluation modes are recommended for preliminary survey measurements. The level recorder mode allows selective measurements at a defined frequency (f_{center}) to determine the field strength caused by a specific RF signal or several signals within a limited frequency range, which means an actual precise measurement. In order to avoid underestimating the exposure during measurements, the Resolution Bandwidth (RBW) should be so adjusted that it is at least the bandwidth of the signal to be measured. Since LTE signals are modulated signals that change in amplitude over time, RMS detectors must be employed for this measurement mode. Peak detectors may lead to overestimation of exposure. The code selective measurement method, which is another measurement method, is based on the measurement of RS signals. The RS signals are radiated by each MIMO antenna at a constant strength. These signals are coded specifically for the cell, and the field strength generated by the RS signals of a MIMO channel per Resource Element (RE) can be easily determined by the process of decoding. Electromagnetic field measurement

devices capable of decoding LTE RS signals should be used to determine the field strength caused by each RS signal. A code selective measurement for an LTE channel only measures the power of an average RS element over the tuned Channel Bandwidth (CBW). For this reason, the CBW value should be chosen equal or less than the bandwidth of the LTE channel to be measured during the measurement [8.8, 8.11]. For example, if an LTE-800 signal with a channel bandwidth of 10 MHz is to be measured, the CBW setting should not be higher than 10 MHz. However, smaller CBW values can be used, and this expedites the measurement process. At the lowest setting of 1.4 MHz (corresponding to a signal bandwidth of 1.08 MHz), the measurement device only decodes the RS signal in the range of 72 subcarriers around the centre frequency. Since the selection of the channel bandwidth will affect the scanning time, the channel bandwidth is usually chosen as 1.4 MHz for the measurements to be performed with the sweeping method. Another important point is to set the correct centre frequency of the LTE channel. Otherwise, the measurement device will not be able to decode the LTE signal correctly and will give relatively low, erratic and unstable results. This frequency information can be received from operators or can be determined quite easily on site by trial and error because the deviation from the channel centre frequency can be a few 100 kHz at most. During the code selective measurement, "Maximum (Max.) Result" type is commonly selected so that the sweeping method can be used to search for the maximum field strength inside a pre-defined volume. Code selective receivers can measure up to four MIMO paths individually (RS 0 to RS 3) and determine how many MIMO paths are used to spread the signals of an LTE cell. The sum of the maximum values of individual RS signals (RS 0 to RS 3) can be used for extrapolation to the maximum output power. For each cell measured, a maximum extrapolation factor (K_i) should be accordingly calculated [8.8, 8.12] by the logarithmic power ratio between the maximum possible channel output power and the average power of an RS element, as given by Eq. 8.4.

$$K_i[dB] = 10 \cdot \log\left(\frac{P_{\max,i}}{P_{RS,i}}\right) \quad (8.4)$$

$$E_{i,\max}[dB\mu V/m] = E_{i,RS}[dB\mu V/m] + K_i[dB] \quad (8.5)$$

After the extrapolation factor K_i is calculated for each antenna, the measurement results are extrapolated with the corresponding extrapolation factor as shown in Eq. 8.5, where, K_i is defined as the extrapolation factor of the antenna i , $P_{\max,i}$ as the maximum power of the antenna i and $P_{RS,i}$ as the power of the reference signal of the antenna i . Also, $E_{i,RS}$ indicates the field strength generated by the RS signal of antenna i , while $E_{i,\max}$ represents the calculated maximum electric field of the antenna i . If during the measurement all subcarriers are set to the same power value (No "RS Boost"), the maximum signal strength will be equal to the RS signal strength per source element times the number of subcarriers. As a result, the extrapolation factor will be the same as the number of subcarriers. In this case, the extrapolation factors calculated according to the ratio of bandwidth of an LTE signal to a subcarrier (15 kHz) and they are presented in Table 8.2. On the other hand, sometimes the subcarriers are not set to the same power value, which is called "RS Boost" where the power of the RS signals is increased by 3 dB. In this case, reduced extrapolation factors should be used as given in Table 8.3 to prevent the overestimation of the exposure level.

Table 8.2: Extrapolation factors (no RS boost)

Channel Bandwidth (CBW)	Signal Bandwidth (SBW)	Extrapolation Factor	Extrapolation Factor (dB)
1.4 MHz	1.08 MHz	72	18.6
3 MHz	2.7 MHz	180	22.6
5 MHz	4.5 MHz	300	24.8
10 MHz	9 MHz	600	27.8
15 MHz	13.5 MHz	900	29.5
20 MHz	18 MHz	1200	30.8

Table 8.3: Extrapolation factors (3 dB RS boost)

Channel Bandwidth (CBW)	Signal Bandwidth (SBW)	Extrapolation Factor	Extrapolation Factor (dB)
1.4 MHz	1.08 MHz	36	15.6
3 MHz	2.7 MHz	90	19.6
5 MHz	4.5 MHz	150	21.8
10 MHz	9 MHz	300	24.8
15 MHz	13.5 MHz	450	26.5
20 MHz	18 MHz	600	27.8

8.3 Measurement Studies

In this study, in order to make a comparison between the two measurements methods, a variety of measurements were carried out in the vicinity of an actual LTE base station as shown in Fig. 8.2. Before starting the measurements, the measurement location where the base station's LTE radiation was detected at the maximum signal level was determined by the broadband and SRM probe. This determined location was designated as a constant measurement point for the comparison between the frequency selective and code selective methods. All the measurements throughout the comparison were performed at this single measurement point instead of the sweeping method where the field probe is continuously moved within a confined volume on the purpose of searching for the maximum radiation. Thereafter, the spectrum of the base station was analysed in a wide band by scanning the entire frequency range in the spectrum mode of the measuring instrument with the aim of discovering all the existing LTE channels. After some investigation, it was detected that there was a dominant 10 MHz LTE channel broadcasting in the frequency range of 811 MHz – 821 MHz frequency range and a dominant 20 MHz LTE channel broadcasting in the frequency range of 1840 MHz – 1860 MHz. Afterwards, the start and end frequencies of the LTE bands were entered sequentially on the measuring device to focus on the LTE spectrums in detail.

Figure 8.2: LTE (4G) Base Station Under Investigation

The measurement of the first LTE channel detected at 816 MHz was started with the frequency selective measurement methods. First of all, the measuring device was set to the spectrum analysis mode and later to the level recorder mode which is deemed to be the most suitable measurement mode for performing frequency selective measurements. In the spectrum analysis mode, the power integration throughout the entire LTE channel was performed with a RBW of 200 kHz and the power average trace was particularly taken as the RMS result. In the level recorder mode, the actual RMS detector was selected on the measurement device in order to perform the frequency selective measurement, and the center frequency was entered as 816 MHz and the RBW value as 10 MHz. Then, the measurement was taken for 6 minutes maximum and the results were recorded. In the second step for the measurement of the LTE channel at 816 MHz, the measurements were repeated with the code selective measurement method. For the code selective measurement, the measurement device is set to the decoding mode. In this code selective measurement mode, before starting the measurement, the central frequency was adjusted to 816 MHz and the CBW value was set to 1.4 MHz instead of 10 MHz as any CBW value smaller than the channel bandwidth is acceptable in LTE measurements to expedite the measurement process. In addition, the measurement range (Meas. Range) of the measuring instrument was duly adjusted in order to display the electric field level properly. On the same measurement

screen, in order to determine the maximum electric field strength emitted by this LTE channel, the extrapolation factor was entered as 600 in accordance with the bandwidth of the channel and Table 8.2 with the assumption of “No RS Boost”. After all the adjustments were made, the measurement was recorded for 6 minutes maximum and compared with the measurement results obtained by the frequency selective method.

After the measurement of the first channel, the similar measurement process was also applied to the LTE channel at 1850 MHz by accordingly and slightly changing the measurement parameters. For this 20 MHz LTE channel, the extrapolation factor was increased to 1200 as per Table 8.2 and the CBW was set to 1.4 MHz for the code selective measurement.

8.4 Measurement Results and Discussions

The measurement results of the first LTE channel at 816 MHz acquired by the frequency selective and code selective measurement methods are given in Fig. 8.3 – 8.5 along with prominent measurement parameters framed in red.

Figure 8.3: Frequency Selective Method Measurement Result by Using Spectrum Analysis Mode for the LTE Channel at 816 MHz

When we first look at the frequency selective measurement results shown in Fig. 8.3 and Fig. 8.4, we see that there is acceptable agreement between the spectrum and the level recorder modes in terms of RMS comparison. While the spectrum analysis mode gives a RMS value of 3.895 V/m with the power integration and a RBW of 200 kHz, the level recorder mode gives a true RMS value of 4.245 V/m with a RBW of 10 MHz. On the other hand, the code selective measurement gives a final value of 11.53 V/m (Fig. 8.4) by using extrapolation factor of 600 and a CBW of 1.4 MHz. The code selective measurement also reveals that the LTE cells broadcasting at 816 MHz have 2-antenna MIMO systems. The reason for the difference between the frequency and code selective measurement modes can be clearly explained with the maximum communication traffic detection feature of the code selective measurement. The spectrum and level recorder modes always give the instantaneous measurement values at the time of the measurement. On the contrary, the code selective measurement has a great advantage of precisely yielding and calculating the maximum radiation level that can be obtained in maximum communication traffic with the aid of the accurate extrapolation factor, which conclusively explains the higher exposure levels detected by the code selective method.

Figure 8.4: Frequency Selective Method Measurement Result by Using Level Recorder Mode for the LTE Channel at 816 MHz

Figure 8.5: Code Selective Method Measurement Result for the LTE Channel at 816 MHz

In a similar manner, the measurement results for the LTE channel at 1850 MHz are presented in Fig. 8.6 – 8.8. There is very good consistency between the spectrum analysis and level recorder modes in terms of RMS comparison. We here used a RBW of 200 kHz for integration in the spectrum analysis mode and a RBW of 20 MHz in the level recorder mode for fully covering this 20 MHz LTE channel at 1850 MHz. At this moment, we need to specially discuss the code selective measurement results of the 1850 MHz LTE channel given in Fig. 8.8. As it is seen in Fig. 8.8, we used an extrapolation factor of 1200 as the targeted channel bandwidth is 20 MHz. The code selective measurement also reveals that the LTE cells broadcasting at 1850 MHz have 4-antenna MIMO systems. Ultimately, we also need to comment on the high number of the decoded LTE cell IDs. As observed in Fig. 8.8, there are many decoded cell IDs among which two cell IDs are dominating. The dominating cell IDs shown in the red frames were probably the cells located inside the targeted base station. The other decoded cells might have been in nearby base stations or might have had antennas facing backwards. However, the cells IDs apart from the dominating ones are not significantly contributing to the final value.

Figure 8.6: Frequency Selective Method Measurement Result by Using Spectrum Analysis Mode for the LTE Channel at 1850 MHz

All the results have shown us that, in the exposure measurements of LTE base stations, the code selective measurement method should be preferred as it can detect the broadcast strength at the maximum communication traffic more accurately. On the other hand, the frequency selective measurement method can still be used as an alternative method in cases where code selective measurement devices are not available or precision is not sought in the measurement results because the instantaneous measurement may cause underestimation of EM exposure and it does not aim for the maximum communication traffic. In fact, there is a special frequency selective method which aims for the maximum traffic in literature to be used in the absence of a code-selective device when the maximum exposure is requested. This special frequency selective extrapolation method tries to estimate the maximum traffic by means of measuring the LTE chimney shown in Fig. 8.9 with a bandwidth of 800 kHz at the centre frequency of the LTE channel and using the extrapolation factor of the “LTE channel signal bandwidth / LTE chimney bandwidth” ratio together with the peak detector instead of the RMS detector [8.4]. This special frequency selective extrapolation method takes it into account that some prominent traffic-independent LTE control signals (P-SS, S-SS and PBCH) occupy the LTE chimney of the channel depicted in Fig. 8.9. However, this method is not considered to be precise. In this research, just for information, we also implemented this special frequency selective extrapolation method that aims to estimate maximum traffic exposure as presented in Fig. 8.10 and 8.11 along with the critical parameters framed in red. As seen in Fig. 8.10 and 8.11, we used a RBW of 800 kHz, a VBW of 2 kHz and the peak detector [8.4]. In addition, an extrapolation factor of 11.72 is included for the 10 MHz LTE channel at 816 MHz while an extrapolation factor of 23.44 is included for the 20 MHz LTE channel at 1850 MHz. When the max peak results in Fig. 8.10 and 8.11 are compared with the code selective results in Fig. 8.5 and 8.8 respectively, it is observed that there is surprisingly acceptable agreement between the code selective and special frequency selective extrapolation method despite the fact that the special frequency selective extrapolation method is not deemed to be precise in comparison to the code selective measurement. At 816 MHz, while the code selective method gives 11.53 V/m, the frequency selective extrapolation method gives 14.75 V/m. Similarly, at 1850 MHz, while the code selective method gives 14.32 V/m, the frequency selective extrapolation method gives 11.06 V/m, which seems acceptable.

Figure 8.7: Frequency Selective Method Measurement Result by Using Level Recorder Mode for the LTE Channel at 1850 MHz

Figure 8.8: Code Selective Method Measurement Result for the LTE Channel at 1850 MHz

Figure 8.9: Example LTE Chimney Used for Frequency Selective Extrapolation [8.4]

Figure 8.10: Special Frequency Selective Extrapolation Method Measurement Result by Using Level Recorder Mode for the LTE Chimney of the Channel at 816 MHz

Figure 8.11: Special Frequency Selective Extrapolation Method Measurement Result by Using Level Recorder Mode for the LTE Chimney of the Channel at 1850 MHz

8.5 Conclusions

In this study scope of the project, frequency selective and code selective measurement methods used for EM pollution measurements of LTE base stations were examined and compared experimentally. Firstly, frequency selective measurements of the LTE (4G) downlink frequency band in the vicinity of a base station were carried out by using the frequency selective mode of a compact electromagnetic field measurement device. Then the measurements were repeated with the code selective measurement method by using the code selective mode of the same measuring device. Finally, comparisons were made between the measurement results acquired by the two methods. When we analysed the comparison results, it was revealed that the measurement results obtained with the code selective measurement method were always higher than the measurement results obtained with the frequency selective measurement method. This is undoubtedly explained by the fact that the code selective method always aims for the maximum traffic whereas the regular frequency selective measurement yields the instantaneous exposure at the time of the measurement. Finally, there is a special frequency selective method that includes extrapolation in literature by means of the LTE chimney measurement, but it is considered imprecise although we acquired its reasonably acceptable comparison with the code selective method. In the light of all the facts mentioned above, we can state that the code selective method should be always the preferred method in LTE base station exposure measurements.

9 Conclusion

This best practice guide has documented the development of calibration capability for electric and magnetic fields over the frequency range from 10 Hz to 40 GHz, covering both low-frequency and high-frequency realization methods and their associated metrological considerations. The work presented demonstrates that such a broad capability cannot be achieved by a single calibration principle, but requires a coordinated set of complementary methods, each adapted to the relevant field quantity, frequency range, field strength, and application constraints.

For low-frequency electric field calibration, the use of parallel plate capacitors has been shown to provide a practical and traceable realization of the electric field for probe and sensor calibration. Two implementations were addressed: a basic method based on a calibrated voltage source, suitable for moderate field strengths, and a method based on a high-voltage generator with voltage divider and digital voltmeter, suitable for significantly higher field levels. The documented procedures confirm that both approaches are technically feasible and can provide comparable levels of uncertainty when the dominant perturbation effects are properly considered.

For low-frequency magnetic field calibration, Helmholtz coil systems remain the principal realization method. The deliverable has described the basic calibration methodology, the associated traceability chain, and the main uncertainty contributions arising from current measurement, coil geometry, spatial field uniformity, probe influence, and environmental background fields. In addition, the work has addressed extensions of the conventional Helmholtz coil concept through single-loop configurations, frequency-range extension methods, and alternative coil geometries supported by simulation. These developments are relevant for broadening the usable frequency range and improving the homogeneous calibration volume.

At higher frequencies, the deliverable has considered a sequence of field-generation environments that enable continuity of calibration capability beyond the quasi-static regime. These include rectangular waveguides, TEM and micro-TEM cells, tapered or pyramidal cells, and fully anechoic room facilities. Each of these methods addresses a different frequency range and a different category of probe or sensor under test. Their inclusion in the present work demonstrates a structured approach to capability building, based on overlapping methods rather than isolated solutions.

A key outcome of the work is the demonstration that calibration capability cannot be defined solely by the availability of field-generation hardware. Traceability must be supported by an unbroken chain linking the generated field to calibrated electrical, geometrical, and transfer quantities, together with a corresponding and well-justified uncertainty evaluation. In this respect, the deliverable has provided practical procedures and uncertainty models for converting laboratory setups into traceable calibration systems. The work therefore contributes not only to facility development, but also to the metrological framework required for reliable and reproducible calibrations.

The uncertainty evaluations presented in the document show that, in many cases, the dominant contributions arise not from the electrical reference quantities themselves, but from field realization and interaction effects. For parallel plate capacitor methods, the major contributions are associated with field inhomogeneity, probe insertion, and the influence of the holder material. For Helmholtz coil methods, the principal effects include field homogeneity, probe influence, and background magnetic fields. In higher-frequency structures and free-space methods, additional contributions arise from mismatch, standing waves, positioning errors, chamber performance, and transfer standard characteristics. These findings confirm that the quality of electromagnetic-field calibration depends critically on the control of the measurement environment and the spatial properties of the generated field.

The reported uncertainty examples indicate that practical and competitive calibration performance can be achieved with the developed methods. For low-frequency electric-field calibration using parallel plate capacitors, typical overall uncertainties of approximately 2.5% of the generated field have been obtained for both the voltage-calibrator method and the high-voltage method. For magnetic-field calibration using Helmholtz coils, similar overall uncertainties of approximately 2.5% have been demonstrated. In the higher-frequency range, lower uncertainties expressed in decibel terms are achievable in certain configurations, provided that the relevant corrections and validation procedures are properly implemented.

The deliverable also shows that the extension of calibration capability to higher frequencies requires methodological adaptation beyond classical low-frequency approaches. In particular, the transition from

conventional multi-turn Helmholtz coils to single-loop structures and higher-frequency current or power-based methods represents an important development for extending magnetic-field calibration capability. Similarly, the use of transfer standards and staged calibration approaches, such as calibration in a micro-TEM cell followed by transfer to other facilities, provides a practical route for maintaining traceability while expanding the operational range of the laboratory.

A further contribution of the work lies in the analysis and optimization of calibration structures through simulation and design studies. The investigation of alternative coil geometries has shown that improved homogeneous field regions can be obtained through optimized design, thereby increasing the useful calibration volume. Such results are relevant for future capability development, as they support a design strategy based on field performance and uncertainty reduction rather than reliance on conventional geometries alone.

In addition to the calibration-focused developments, the deliverable has addressed the application of electromagnetic field measurement methods in practical exposure assessment, including measurements of signals from telecommunication base stations. This part of the work provides useful context by illustrating how the quality and suitability of the measurement method influence the interpretation of electromagnetic field levels in real environments. Although this topic is application-oriented, it supports the broader objective of the project by linking calibration capability with the reliability of field measurements performed in practice.

Overall, the work reported in this best practice guide has established a coherent basis for electromagnetic field calibration capability covering a broad frequency range and multiple types of calibration facilities. The methods described are mutually complementary and together form an integrated capability chain extending from low-frequency field generation based on voltage and current standards to higher-frequency realizations based on transmission-line structures, waveguides, and free-space techniques. The document therefore provides both a technical reference and a practical implementation basis for laboratories seeking to establish, improve, or extend traceable calibration services for electric- and magnetic-field probes and sensors.

In conclusion, this best practice guide has achieved its objective of documenting the methods and metrological basis for building calibration capability for electric and magnetic fields from 10 Hz to 40 GHz. The work confirms that reliable capability in this area depends on the coordinated use of appropriate field-generation methods, rigorous traceability, careful validation of field conditions, and comprehensive uncertainty evaluation. The results presented provide a sound foundation for further implementation, interlaboratory comparability, and future extension of electromagnetic field calibration services within the project and beyond

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